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Éditorial

Jean-François GERKENS

La rédaction de la *RIDA* désire dédier son 66^e numéro au grand romaniste amstellodamois qu'était Hans Ankum. Dans notre éditorial précédent, nous soulignons le choc causé par sa disparition. Cette fois, nous désirons insister sur l'importance qu'il a eue — et aura encore — pour le monde scientifique dans les domaines des droits de l'antiquité en général, et pour la *RIDA* et la SIHDA en particulier. *L'in memoriam* qui lui est consacré dans le présent numéro insiste particulièrement sur son rôle au sein de la SIHDA. D'autres textes commémorant Hans Ankum paraîtront sous la plume Jeroen Chorus (dans *IVRA*) et de Laurens Winkel (dans *INDEX*) et permettront de compléter un peu le tableau de son œuvre.

Au moment de rédiger cet éditorial, il est inévitable de dire un mot à propos de l'impact de la pandémie de la Covid-19 sur notre travail éditorial. Il faut malheureusement bien constater qu'elle a ralenti la distribution de la *RIDA* 65 et l'édition de la *RIDA* 66. Quant à son impact sur la SIHDA, elle a malheureusement obligé les organisateurs — en accord avec le comité directeur de la Société Fernand De Visscher — à renoncer à organiser notre 74^e session internationale à Santiago du Chili en janvier 2021 comme c'était prévu. Cette session sera dès lors reportée d'un an et organisée en janvier 2022. La 75^e session internationale prévue à Bruxelles et Gand en septembre 2021 est également reportée d'un an, c'est-à-dire au mois de septembre 2022. Espérons que le futur proche nous permettra de nous retrouver tous en bonne santé et dans l'ambiance chaleureuse qui caractérise nos congrès !

Excellente lecture à toutes et tous !

Chaufontaine, le 23 juin 2020.

De incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata.
Origins, Context and Legal Treatment of
Shipwrecking in Roman Law*

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1. Introduction

The Mediterranean has been perceived as a border and a place of conflict, but also as a bridge, relating to all those who lived on its shores. This paper considers both conceptions. This work aims to briefly describe the origin, background, and possible chronological dating of the edict *de incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata* (hereinafter, *edictum de naufragio*), which punished robberies that took advantage of catastrophic situations such as fire, wreck, or assault of a ship. Therefore, I will first introduce how shipwrecking activities were allowed and favoured by the archaic governments of the different Mediterranean areas. Secondly, I will address the progressive repression of this practice as the different populations of the Mediterranean interacted with each other, either through political or commercial relations. This paper will address other related issues, such as the development of the praetor's edict and the solutions imposed by the praetorian law to address violent conflicts. Therefore, the analysis of this phenomenon relates to different problems such as the risks of navigation or the control of piracy by the Roman Republican government.

2. *Ius naufragii*

Ius naufragii (literally, “the right to wreck”) constituted an archaic practice, by which the shipwreck or its remains reaching a foreign coast outside a port recognized as such¹, belonged to those who took them as their own. By virtue of the

* I would like to thank Professor Carlos Sánchez-Moreno, Professor Jean-François Gerkens and Professor Gianfranco Purpura, whose comments and suggestions made during my PhD have improved this piece immeasurably. Any errors that remain are, of course, my own responsibility.

1. With the statement “recognized as such” I do not refer only to commercial ports or emporia, but to those ports recognized by a community in which the navigator could achieve protection. For the case of *emporion*, see: J. VELISSAROPOULOS-KARAKOSTAS, “Le monde de l’emporion”, *DHA* 3 (1977), p. 61–85; D. DEMETRIOU, *Negotiating Identity in the Ancient Mediterranean: The*

ius naufragii, the remains from the wreckage belonged either to the one who took them or to the community, coast or riverbank where it occurred². This practice began as an individual right, but developed as a right of the diverse communities from the Mediterranean³, who found in this activity a way of subsistence⁴, enrichment and affirmation of their power⁵. Several sources describe how the wreckers were generally located near reefs⁶, and even a passage by Xenophon tells how the inhabitants of Salmidesos delimited the borders of the coast in order to share what came to their banks from the shipwrecks⁷. It could also happen that the coastal inhabitants attracted the ship to the shoreline, and that when disembarking; they took away all their property, killed or enslaved them⁸. Literary sources mention

Archaic and Classical Greek Multiethnic Emporia, Cambridge, 2005; ID., “What is an emporion? A reassessment”, *Historia* 60–3 (2011), p. 255–272; G. CHIC GARCÍA, “Violencia legal y no legal en el marco del estrecho de Gibraltar”, in A. ÁLVAREZ-OSSORIO RIVAS, E. FERRER ALBELDA, E. GARCÍA VARGAS (eds.), *Piratería y seguridad Marítima en el Mediterráneo Antiguo*, Seville, 2013, p. 18; A.J. DOMÍNGUEZ MONEDERO, “Piratería en Magna Grecia y Sicilia: mecanismos de prevención y contención”, in A. ÁLVAREZ-OSSORIO RIVAS, E. FERRER ALBELDA, E. GARCÍA VARGAS (eds.), *Piratería y seguridad Marítima en el Mediterráneo Antiguo*, Seville, 2013, p. 71–75. Although late, a fragment of Ulpian (D. 50.16.59.68 *ad ed.*) indicates that the term *portus* designates a closed and safe space where goods were exported and imported. Considering the context of the fragment (*EP*³, § 22) Ulpian referred to the practices carried out in rivers characterized as public. Therefore, it did not necessarily refer to the fact that the port should be a large commercial centre with a highly developed infrastructure, but a protected space where imports and exports could be handled. In that sense, the ports were not only places with a physical design, but also with a human infrastructure related to these practices (cf. Philost. *Vit. Apol.*, 12.6).

2. Strab. 17.3.20; about the Eubean coast.
3. Cf. L. ANDRICH, “Naufragio”, *DI XV-2*, Turin, 1904–1911, p. 1303–1355.
4. ANDRICH, *o.c.* (n. 3), p. 1303–55; C.M. MOSCHETTI, “Naufragio”, *ED 27*, Milan, 1977, p. 547–58; J. VELISSAROPOULOS-KARAKOSTAS, *Les nauclères grecs : recherches sur les institutions maritimes en Grèce et dans l’Orient hellénisé*, Paris, 1980, p. 162; P. JANNI, *Il mare degli antichi*, Bari, 1996, p. 331–343 (*viaggio fortunoso e naufragio*); p. 373–401 (*i passeggeri a bordo*); p. 453–470 (*acque lontane e perigliose*). The first written proof of the *ius naufragii* comes from the XIth cent. BC, from the papyrus Wenamon (P. Moskau 120). It was found in 1891 near El-Hibeh, and acquired by the Egyptologist Wladimir Golenischeff, who provided a first translation (*LAE* 145, 155). The papyrus tells how the Egyptian ambassador Unamon, from the time of Ramses XI, was sent as manager to get wood to build the new statue of the god Amon for the sacred festival of Thebes. For more details, see L. CASSON, *The Ancient Mariners*, Princeton, 1992, p. 46–57. On his side, M.H. FANTAR, *Fenici e Cartaginesi*, Milan, 1997, p. 13–16; and ID., “I Fenici”, in M. GUIDETTI (ed.), *Storia del Mediterraneo nell’antichità: IX–I secolo a.C.*, Milan, 2004, p. 18 has considered the tale fictitious. However, even if the story is fictional, the document witnesses the practice of the *ius naufragii* in the Mediterranean.
5. CHIC GARCÍA, *o.c.* (n. 1), p. 17.
6. Aesch. *PB*, 726s.; Sophocles. *Ant.*, 926; Dio Chrys. *Eub.*, 32.
7. Xen. *Anab.*, 7.5.2.
8. Hdt. 3.137.138.

this sort of practice⁹, and the existence of coastal areas with a large number of wrecks sunk near the sandy shores probably indicates that shipwrecking vessels by attracting them to the coast with signs was usual¹⁰. A fragment from Ulpian (D. 47.9.10)¹¹ reveals that these methods were still in use in the third century AD, and probably also later.

I need to address the differences between *ius naufragii* and piracy¹², since the latter takes on different meanings depending on the historical and social context of practice. As both actions were frequently committed against foreign ships, there is no clear distinction between them even in the literary sources¹³. I have previously indicated what *ius naufragii* consisted of, and as for piracy, before the Roman Republic it constituted a form of private violence, not protected by the state, although when practised endemically, it was common for many of those involved in such actions to be both merchants and pirates¹⁴. The existence of

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9. Apollod. *Epit.*, 6, 7; Amian. *RG*, 2, 2–3; Polib. 2, 8; Plin. *Nat. Hist.*, 2.73 (71) e 7.57.11; Strab. 4.1.58; 13.1.174; Dion. *Biz. Perieg. Fragm.*, 47–49.
 10. G. PURPURA, “Rinvenimenti sottomarini nella Sicilia occidentale”, *Archeologia subacquea* 3, (1986), p. 156.
 11. D. 47.9.10: *Ne piscatores nocte lumine ostenso fallant navigantes, quasi in portum aliquem delaturi, eoque modo in periculum naves et qui in eis sunt deducant sibiue execrandam praedam parent, praesidis provinciae religiosa constantia efficiat*. Another possibility for the thieves was to extinguish the fire of a nearby lighthouse and to light it next to it in order to wreck the ships (Strab. 4.1.8).
 12. J.M. SESTIER, *La piraterie dans l'antiquité*, Paris, 1880, p. 40, “la piraterie à une époque où la loi était encore inconnue, où l'homme était dans la première phase de son existence, aux prises avec les nécessités de la vie, n'avait pas un caractère odieux, c'était un métier comme un autre”; J. ROUGÉ, “Le droit de naufrage et ses limitations en Méditerranée avant l'établissement de la domination à Rome”, in *Mél. Piganiol* 3, Paris, 1966, p. 1468.
 13. D. 49.15.24 (Ulp. 1 *Inst.*); D. 50.16.118 (Pomp. 2 *ad Q. Mucium*); Thuc. 1, 5; Cic. *Off.*, 3.28.73; Cic. *Ver.*, 7.28.73; Cic. *S. Rosc.*, 50.146; and also, by E. RUGGIERO, G. BARBIERI, “Latrones”, *Dizionario epigrafico di antichità romane*, vol. 4, Rome, 1946, p. 460–6; H.A. ORMEROD, *Piracy in the Ancient World*, Baltimore, 1967, p. 61; T. HONORÉ, *Ulpian*, Oxford, 1982, p. 247; L. CAVAZZUTI, “La pirateria nella navigazione antica”, in M. GIACOBELLI (ed.), *Lezioni Fabio Faccenna II. Conferenze di archeologia subacquea (III–V ciclo)*, Bari, 2004, p. 45. Besides, Ulpian has been considered as an author who was not very systematic when writing by A. PERNICE, “Ulpian als Schriftsteller”, *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin XXV* (1885), p. 443–484 (=Labeo 8, [1962], p. 351–389).
 14. For example, Menelaus' expeditions included piracy as an additional activity (Thuc. 1.5); on the other hand, Thucydides described Minos of Crete as the first suppressor of piracy (Thuc. 1.4). While Demosthenes described pirate attacks on commercial ships (Dem. 53, 3ss.), Euripides highlighted the role of Nauplio (Eur. *Hel.*, 765–769; 1125–1129) as pirate and destroyer of ships (Ps.-Apollod. *Bibl.*, 2.1.5). For his part, Homer makes the reader aware that both Jason and Ulysses committed acts of piracy during their maritime journeys (Hom. *Od.*, 3.69; 12.68; 14). According to Lysias, for the merchant there was not much difference between the type of accident caused by shipwreck or piracy; both were an unfortunate event that forced him to recover if he survived (Lys., 22.14); Arist. *Pol.*, 1.1256a. In ancient times, piracy was not something shameful, indeed it brought an element of glory (Thuc. 1.5; Hom. *Od.*, III. 71–4). The

pirate-merchants, as well as the practice of *ius naufragii* were maintained while the Mediterranean communities did not intend to fully develop their trade with other regions¹⁵. These regions could avoid shipwrecking, at least when the owner of the wrecked ship came from a known region¹⁶. Piracy begins to be differentiated from war in the classical Greek period (v–iv BC), when the political interests of the Greek city begin predominate against the interest to attack and spoil¹⁷. Little by little, large populations began to boost traffic at their ports; and to establish control measures in these for the entry and exit of the ships, the transport of goods was carried out with the protection of the community¹⁸. Notwithstanding that, ancient

Illyrians, for example, considered piracy to be a practice that honoured them (Plb. 2.8–9; 2.4–5); A. GUILLERM. *La marine dans l'antiquité*, Paris, 1975, p. 19–24.

15. K. POLANYI, *Trade and Markets in the Early Empires*, Illinois, 1957, p. 126, who indicates that according to Aristotle's texts it can be seen that trading is "natural" when it serves to maintain the community and make it self-sufficient. The need for trade arises when a family grows too large and its members are forced to live separately. His self-sufficiency would now be greatly hampered if it were not for the operation of surrendering a part of the surplus itself. The *ius naufragii* in Greece was practised in areas that were outside the influence of the big πόλις, J. VELISSAROPOULOS-KARAKOSTAS, *o.c.* (n. 4), p. 158–159.
16. That fact is perceivable through the inscription collected by H. VAN EFFENTERRE, "Querelles crétoises", *REA* 44 (1942), p. 32–40 (*Inscr. Cret.* I, XVI, no. 4 B = *Inscr. Delos*, 1513 B), the autor mentions that it should be a foreign ship, due to its weight and volume. See also J. VELISSAROPOULOS-KARAKOSTAS, *o.c.* (n. 4), p. 161. A curious fact occurred in Knossos, in the second century BC, where there was a conflict between the Cretan cities of Olonte and Lato over a territorial issue. A ship was wrecked on its shores and the ownership of the cargo (silver coins, bronze armour, a slave and two free men sold as slaves) was contested by both communities that disputed the ownership of the ship following the principle of *ius naufragii*.
17. Ph. DE SOUZA, "Piracy", in *OCD*, Oxford, 2012, p. 1149; some shipwrecks evidence this kind of response, as is the case of a Kyrenia ship (310–300 BC), located a short distance off the coast of Cyprus, where spears were found embedded in the outer part of the keel; P. POMEY, P.A. GIANFROTTA, *Archeologia subacquea: storia, tecnica, scoperte e relitti*, Milan, 1981, p. 168–169; S. KATZEV, *The Ancient Ship of Kyrenia, Beneath Cyprus Seas. Great Moments in Greek Archaeology*, Oxford, 2007, p. 286–299; J.P. DELGADO (ed.), *Encyclopaedia of Underwater and Maritime Archaeology*, London, 1997, p. 227–228. The dating and location of the ship relates it to the wars between the *diadochi*, so it is not ruled out that this ship was attacked by a warship. Cf. Diod. 18.2. 3–4; 9; 16–24; P. ARNAUD, "L'antiquité classique et la piraterie", in G. BUTI, P. HRODÉJ (eds.), *Histoire des pirates et des corsaires. De l'antiquité à nos jours*, Paris, 2016, p. 54.
18. Dem. 88. 53–6; Plut. *Cim.*, 7; J. HASEBROEK, *Staat und handel im alten Griechenland*, Tübingen, 1928, p. 149. The port should provide speedy service and more than merely legal procedures to resolve any controversies in order to attract trade (Xenoph. *On revenues*, 355). The presence of authorities concerning controversies guaranteed the security of trading operations, and consequently the port would be more attractive for merchants and customers. These authorities could be from the *polis* located near the port, or from the port itself, according to the distinction established by in A. BRESSON, P. ROUILLARD (eds.), *L'Emporion*, Paris, 1993, p. 163–226. K. VLASSOPOULOS, I.K. XYDOPOULOS, "Introduction", in K. VLASSOPOULOS, E. TOUNTA, I.K. XYDOPOULOS (eds.), *Violence and Community: Law, Space and Identity in the Ancient Eastern Mediterranean world*, London, 2015, p. 10–11: "But equally significant is how many communities constructed their identity in explicit link to the suppression of piracy (...) this

societies established some limitations to the *ius naufragii* before Rome established its hegemony on the Mediterranean¹⁹, by using practices that sought compensation for the damage caused, or building relationships with other populations²⁰. These practices were the ἀνδρολεψία²¹, σύλαν²², or the use of συμβολα²³. The first two

last aspect points to the link between violence and space: suppressing piracy and brigandage is necessarily connected to control over territory and routes (...).”

19. As the paper entitled indicated: ROUGÉ, *o.c.* (n. 12), p. 1467–1479.
20. A practice that we have classified separately is the *asylia*, because it has more relation with commerce than with the uses for the maintenance of the coexistence or the creation of bonds *inter gens*. V. MAROTTA, “La tutela dello scambio e commerci mediterranei in età arcaica e repubblicana”, *Ostraka V–1* (1996), p. 6: at first, trade was performed in particular places, such as sanctuaries, separated from the urban area itself, so that commercial relations were placed under the protection of a god. According to G. GLOTZ, *The Greek City and its Institutions*, London, 1929, p. 267, *symbolon* evolved from the right of *asylia*. See also D. VAN BERCHEM, “Trois cas d’asylie archaïque”, *Museum Helveticum* 17 (1960), p. 21–33; K.J. RIGSBY, *Asylia: Territorial Inviolability in the Hellenistic World*, Berkeley, 1997.
21. Demost. 21.82; 23.82–4; Pol. 8.50–1; *Lexeis Rhetorikai* in *Lex. Seg.* 213–30; B. BRAVO, “*Androlepsia*. La ‘prise d’hommes’ comme vengeance d’un meurtre commis dans une cité étrangère”, in J. MODRZEJEWSKI, D. LIEBS (eds.), *Symposion. Actes du III^e colloque international d’Histoire du Droit grec et hellénistique*, (1977), p. 133–156; D.M. MACDOWELL, *Athenian Homicide law in the age of the orators*, Manchester, 1963, p. 27–28; J. VELISSAROPOULOS-KARAKOSTAS, *o.c.* (n. 4), p. 141–150.
22. Through the exercise of σύλαν, any citizen (or city) who considers himself injured by a foreign community or a citizen of the latter, could exercise a compensatory action against it, C. GIOFFREDI, “In tema di *iniuria*”, in *Nuovi studi di diritto greco e romano*, Rome, 1980, p. 169, the σύλαν is also called ῥυσιάζειν, or generally called ἄγειν, is similar to the *manus iniectio* according to the autor, because in its privativistic sphere is the widest concept of *iniuria* or ἀδικεῖν that exists; G. PURPURA, “*Ius naufragii, sylai e lex Rhodia*. Genesi delle consuetudini marittime mediterranee”, *AUPA* 47 (2002), p. 275–292. See B. BRAVO, “*Sulân*. Représailles et justice privée contre des étrangers dans les cités grecques”, *ANSP* 3 (1980), p. 675–987; A. CASSAYRE, “La justice sur les pierres. Recueil d’inscriptions à caractère juridique des cités grecques à l’époque hellénistique”, *BCH* 122 (1998), see <http://journals.openedition.org/criminocorpus/2954>; M.F. BASLEZ, *L’étranger dans la Grèce antique*, Paris, 2008, p. 152; also, see *IG II² 1132*; *IG IV², 1 68*; *FD III, 2 68*; *SGDI II 2506*; *CID 4 12*; *CID 4 114*; *IG IX I², 2 573*; *IG XII, 9 191*; *IMT Skam/ NebTaeler 192*; *SEG II 533*. An example of this practice is found in the letter of Aquilodorus (*SEG XL 609*), in which he narrates how, in a trip that was carried out by Anaxagoras, his position was confiscated by Matasys, by virtue of the right of reprisal, M. DILLON, L. GARLAND, *Ancient Greece: Social and Historical Documents from Archaic Times to the Death of Alexander the great*, New York, 2010, p. 164; P. CECCARELLI, *Ancient Greek Letter Writing: A Cultural History (600 BC–150 BC)*, Oxford, 2013, p. 38.
23. In the context of my research, συμβολόν refers to a document that represented the granting of a hospitality act by two members of different communities, and sealed the relationship of friendship established between both, D.L. *Vit.phil.*, IV.46.9; X.150; Eur. *Orest.*, 1130; Eur. *Rh.*, 220; Plut. *Phil.*, XIV.5.5; XV.7.2; XXI.9.2; XXX.8.2; *Marc.*, XXVI. 1.2; *Pyrrh.*, XX.3.1; G.E.M. DE STE CROIX, “Notes on Jurisdiction in the Athenian Empire, I”, *Classical Quarterly* 11–1 (1962), p. 94–111; “Notes on Jurisdiction in the Athenian Empire, II”, *Classical Quarterly* 11–2 (1962), p. 268–280; G. PURPURA, “Il naufragio nel diritto romano, problemi giuridici e testimonianze archeologiche”, *AUPA* 43 (1995), p. 468–469, paper in which he indicates that

refer to a sort of “right of reprisal”, which could penalize foreigners for damages committed by themselves or their community of origin, by kidnapping people (ἀνδρολεψία) or property (σύλαν²⁴). On the other hand, the σύμβολον embodied a liaison established between individuals or their communities of origin.

In short, both *ius naufragii* and piracy were conceived by their practitioners as means of subsistence until they gradually defined a concept for these practices as acts of private violence. Later on, these practices were officially identified as unlawful by Roman jurisprudence through dispositions such as the *edictum de naufragio* from the late Roman Republic. At this time, pillage and shipwreck were characterized as violent actions opposing the legal framework defined by Rome, which had hegemony in the Mediterranean and had begun to establish the bases of its Mediterranean conquest²⁵. Although they could remain isolated areas that kept on exercising the *ius naufragii* during the Roman Empire, it will not be until its fall that the barbarian populations will recurrently commit shipwrecking²⁶. According to Rougé, the *ius naufragii* was still recognized during the Roman Empire²⁷, a controversial opinion with which I must disagree. Although the assault on ships must have continued to be committed during the empire, this practice was not

the first σύμβολον found in a shipwreck corresponds to that of Ulu Burun, in which a gold ring divided in two was found, which has been identified as an intentionally fragmented seal. However, it is common to find rings used as σύμβολα, see J.W. JONES, *The law and Legal Theory of the Greeks: an introduction*, Oxford, 1956, p. 217; P. GAUTHIER, *Symbola. Les étrangers et la justice dans les cités grecques*, Nancy, 1972; J. VELISSAROPOULOS-KARAKOSTAS, “Les symbola d'affaires. Remarques sur les tablettes archaïques de l'île de Corfou”, in *Symposion 1977*, Vienna, 1982, p. 71–83; S. CATALDI, *Symbolai e relazioni tra le città greche nel v sec. a.C.*, Pisa, 1983; G. HERMAN, *Ritualised Friendship and the Greek City*, Cambridge, 1987, works that display the different forms that the *symbolon* could adopt; F. ZUCCOTTI, “*Symbolon e stipulatio*”, in *Testimonium amicitiae*, Milan, 1992, p. 305–439; R.J. HOPPER, P.C. MILLET, “*Symbolon*”, in *OCD*, Oxford, 2016, p. 1563.

24. Y. GARLAN, *Guerre et économie en Grèce ancienne*, Paris, 1999, p. 108.
25. The reduction of piracy also involved a change in shipbuilding, as smaller ships began to be built, see D. ABULAFIA, *The Great Sea: A Human History of the Mediterranean*, Oxford, 2011, p. xxx; D. SCHIAPPOLI, “Il *ius naufragii* secondo il diritto della Chiesa”, *RDN* 6 (1938) p. 137–157; V. SCIALOJA, “Naufragio”, in *NDI* 8, Turin, 1939, p. 865–869, G. PURPURA, *o.c.* (n. 22), p. 290; D. 41.2.21.1–2 (Iav. 7 *ex Cassio*); D. 14.2.2.8 (Paul. 34 *ad ed*); D. 14.2.8 (Iul. 2 *ex Minicio*); D. 41.1.9.8 (Gaius *Lib 2 rerum cott.*); D. 41.7.7 (Iul. 2 *ex Minicio*); D. 47.2.43.11 (Ulp. 41 *ad Sab.*); I. 2.1.46; contra, J. ROUGÉ, *Recherches sur l'organisation du commerce maritime en Méditerranée sous l'Empire romain*, Paris, 1966, p. 339–340.
26. C.M. MOSCHETTI, *o.c.* (n. 4), p. 551–2, quoting several examples such as Gregory of Tours, *Hist. Franc.*, 6, 2; *Brev. Al.*, 7. 2. 18; even if in Byzantine law were several dispositions, which were similar to the Roman ones, Bas. 53, 3 and *Nomos Rhodion*, III, 45–47. In addition, about that compilation, see W. ASHBURNER, *Nomos Rhodion Nautikos: The Rhodian Sea-Law*, Oxford, 1909.
27. J. ROUGÉ, *o.c.* (n. 12), p. 1478–1479.

recognized and accepted by the imperial government as a right of its people²⁸. In sum, it is not possible to characterize the *ius naufragii* or piracy simply as “armed violence exercised through the use of ships”, since violence does not depend solely on the force exerted over something or someone, but also on the characterization of these actions in different places²⁹. In that sense, the criminalization and prosecution of piracy would not be based on principles of natural law, but rather on unilateral solutions to act against specific situations³⁰, and closely related to the notion, if not of empire, at least of politically organised community³¹.

3. The historic-juridical context of the edict *de naufragio*

This section studies other related issues such as the development of the praetor’s edict, and above all, the solutions imposed by this magistrate to deal with situations of private violence. In this way, the analysis of this phenomenon is related to various issues such as the risks of navigation, or the control of piracy during the Roman Republic. Finally, the analysis of the features and contexts of creation of the praetorian edict will help characterize this historical phase, when various events affected the creation of law.

The last century of the Republic is known for its violent events, such as the disturbances resulting from the domination of Sulla³², the civil wars³³, the constant

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28. Consistent with SCIALOJA, *o.c.* (n. 19), p. 865; PURPURA, *o.c.* (n. 23), p. 475; ID., “Relitti di navi e diritti del fisco. Una congettura sulla *lex Rhodia*”, *AUPA* 36 (1976), p. 73–75.
 29. This definition is given by PH. DE SOUZA. “Greek piracy”, in A. POWELL (ed.), *The Greek world*, London, 1995, p. 180; ID., *Piracy in the Graeco-Roman World*, Cambridge, 1999, p. 10–11; CHIC GARCÍA, *o.c.* (n. 1), p. 31–49; ARNAUD, *o.c.* (n. 17), p. 22.
 30. L. BENTON, “Toward a New Legal History of Piracy: Maritime Legalities and the Myth of Universal Jurisdiction”, *International Journal of Maritime History* 23–1 (2011), p. 239–240.
 31. A. POLICANTE, *The Pirate Myth: Genealogies of an Imperial Concept*, London, 2015, p. xii.
 32. Plut. *Sulla*, XXXI; K. CHRIST, *Sulla: eine römische Karriere*, Munich, 2005, p. 21ss. A. KEAVENEY, *Sulla: The Last Republican*, London/New York, 2013, p. 124–128.
 33. P.A. BRUNT, *Social Conflicts in the Roman Republic*, London, 1971, p. 116.

threat of pirates³⁴, the servile revolt of Spartacus³⁵, or the return of Pompey³⁶. In this context, both the military and diplomatic forces from Rome managed to impose order on the previous state of anarchy affecting diverse areas of the Mediterranean³⁷. Despite the violence and the latent crisis, the last years of the

34. L. MONACO, *Persecutio piratarum. Battaglie ambigue e svolte costituzionali nella Roma repubblicana*, Naples, 1996, p. 78. Although it is well known that Rome established client relationships with pirates for their economic interests in the slave market, in this case we will focus on the behavior aimed at repressing it with the intention of developing commercial traffic, cf. E. BADIAN, *Foreign clientele*, Oxford, 1958, p. 287; J. ROUGÉ, *o.c.* (n. 12), p. 1467–1479; M. MARTINA, “Le clientele piratiche di Pompeo”, in A. HEUSS (ed.), *La rivoluzione romana, inchiesta tra gli antichisti*, Naples, 1982, p. 175–185; E. DENIAUX, *Clientèles et pouvoir à l’époque de Cicéron*, Paris, 1993, p. 184–190; J.J. AUBERT, “Commerce”, in D. JOHNSTON, *The Cambridge Companion to Roman law*, Cambridge, 2015, p. 220. The results provided by underwater archeology have been interpreted as proof of the intensity of piracy during the 1st cent. BC. Several shipwrecks contained weapons that could have been transported by subjects in charge of the protection of the ship (D. 4.9.1.3 [Ulp. 14 *ad ed.*]). In addition, the studies of both Gianfrotta and Parker have revealed an increase in shipwrecks at this time. Cf. N. LAMBOGLIA, “La nave Romana di Albenga. Storia e vicende della scoperta”, *Rivista di studi liguri* 18–34 (1952), p. 131–236; *Albenga romana e medievale*, Albenga, 1957, p. 138–139; “Il saccheggio della nave romana di Spargi”, *Rivista di studi liguri* 30 (1964), p. 258–266; L. CAVAZUTTI, “Nuovi rinvenimenti sottomarini per lo studio della pirateria”, in *Archeologia subacquea, studi, ricerche e documenti*, Roma, 1997, p. 197–214; C. BELTRAME, “A review of the Roman wreck of Spargi (Sassari/Italy): an evidence of the commerce of luxurious furniture during Late-Republican Age”, in *Schutz des Kulturerbes unter Wasser. Veränderungen europäischer Lebenskultur durch Fluß- und Seehandel. Beiträge zum Internationalen Kongress für Unterwasserarchäologie (IKUWA ’99), 18–21.02.1999 Sassnitz. Beitr. Ur- u. Frühgesch. Mecklenburg-Vorpommern* 35, Lübstorf, 2000, p. 155–162; P.A. GIANFROTTA, “Fantasmi sottomarini: guerre, pirateria...o chissà cos’altro”, *Daidalos. Studi e ricerche del Dipartimento di Scienze del Mondo antico* III, Viterbo, 2001, p. 212; “Pirateria e archeologia sottomarina: rinvenimenti, luoghi e circostanze”, in A. ÁLVAREZ-OSSORIO RIVAS, E. FERRER ALBELDA, E. GARCÍA VARGAS (eds.), *Piratería y seguridad marítima en el mediterráneo antiguo*, Sevilla, 2013, p. 51–66; P.A. GIANFROTTA, “Commerci e Pirateria: Prime Testimonianze Archeologiche Sottomarine”, *MEFRA* 93–1 (1981), p. 227–242; A.J. PARKER, *Ancient Shipwreck of the Mediterranean and the Roman Provinces*, Rome, 1992. P. ARNAUD, *o.c.* (n. 17), correctly points out that although the archaeological evidence shows that the wrecked ship suffered a violent attack, it does not necessarily mean a pirate attack towards this ship, *o.c.* (n. 17), p. 22; in my opinion, these remains are a sample of the violence prevailing in the sea in this period, and although the interference of pirates is not clear, other sources show the intensity of their activity. Who could be, according to the Digest: D. 4.9.1.3 (Ulp. 14 *ad ed.*) *Et sunt quidam in navibus, qui custodiae gratia navibus praeponuntur, ut naufulakes et diaetarii. Si quis igitur ex his receperit, puto in exercitorem dandam actionem, quia is, qui eos huiusmodi officio praeponit, committi eis permittit, quamquam ipse navicularius vel magister id faciat, quod xeirimbolon appellant. Sed et si hoc non exercet, tamen de recepto navicularius tenebitur*. The presence of armed men on board is also mentioned by Amian. 15.2.2–3; Polyb. 2.8; or Strab. 89.5.2.669
35. B. SHAW, *Spartacus and the Slave Wars*, London, 2001; N. FIELDS, *Spartacus and the Slave War 73–71 BC: A Gladiator rebels against Rome*, London, 2009.
36. Cic. *Caec.*, 140.
37. A. ECKSTEIN, *Mediterranean Anarchy, Interstate War, and the Rise of Rome*, London, 2006, p. 3–5, 176.

Republic were a period of great legal activity³⁸, although what is still unclear is whether the access to justice at this time would have been something simple to achieve³⁹.

Different scholars have tried to describe the evolution of the praetorian edict, as in the case of Dernburg, who characterized the evolution of the edict in three *strata*, according to the language used in the text⁴⁰. Daube also took that approach, moving through more general lines (defined as “forms of legislation”), and indicating that the evolution of the edict involved the passage of a conditional clause to a relative one⁴¹. Kelly mentioned Dernburg’s theory, but advocated a somewhat simpler reconstruction: taking into account the moment when the edict began to modify substantive rights (according to him in the last century of the Republic), and in that sense, tracing an evolution from adjective to substantive law by focusing on the language used in the edict⁴². Otherwise, Alan Watson compiled different key facts (see table 3) that according to his point of view could help to decipher the logic employed by the praetors when publishing the edict⁴³.

Another element to bear in mind is that the praetor commonly included in his edict other legal remedies such as *restitutiones in integrum*, *stipulationes* (e.g.

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38. A. SHERWIN-WHITE, “Violence in Roman Politics”, *JRS* 46, 1–2 (1956), p. 7; A.W. LINTOTT, *Violence in Republican Rome*, Oxford, 1968, p. 22–34; L. LABRUNA, *Vim fieri veto: alle radici de una ideologia*, Naples, 1971, p. 6–27; “Les racines de l’idéologie répressive de la violence dans l’histoire du droit romain”, *Index* 3 (1972), p. 525–538; A. WATSON, *Law Making in the Roman Republic*, Oxford, 1974, p. 32–33; B. FRIER, “Urban Praetors and Rural Violence: The Legal Background of Cicero’s *Pro Caecina*”, *TAPA* 113 (1983), p. 238; Id., *The Rise of the Roman Jurists: Studies in Cicero’s Pro Caecina*, Princeton, 1985, p. 45–46; A. RIGGSBY, *Crime and community in Ciceronian Rome*, Austin, 1999, chap. 4; C. WILLIAMSON, *The Laws of the Roman People. Public law in the expansion and decline of the Roman Republic*, Michigan, 2005, p. 350–357; C. MOATTI, *The Birth of Critical Thinking in Republican Rome*, Cambridge, 2015, p. 10, 96.
39. MOATTI, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 10; 96; P.J. DU PLESSIS, *Cicero’s Law: Rethinking Roman Law of the Late Republic*, Edinburgh, 2016, p. 5. However, access to magistrates also seems uneasy even in the Imperial period, cf. E. METZGER, “Having an audience with the magistrate”, in F. DE ANGELIS (ed.), *Spaces of Justice in the Roman World*, Leiden, 2010, p. 39.
40. H. DERNBURG, “Untersuchungen über das Alter der einzelnen Satzungen des prätorischen Edikts”, in *Festgabe August Wilhelm Heffner*, Berlin, 1873, p. 105–107. The earliest phase constituted a prohibition, then a promise of action against a “transgressor”. The intermediate phase is represented by an edict in which the prohibition is not established, but can be implied by the promise of a remedy. Finally, the last phase, in which we find an edict where the conditional clause is indirect in the sense that the remedy depends to a greater extent, not on a fact, but on the claim of the plaintiff that an event has occurred.
41. D. DAUBE, *Forms of Roman legislation*, Oxford, 1956, p. 6. First, then, in early Roman legislation, the form “if a man murders another man, he shall be put to death” predominates, whereas later, the form “whoever murders a man shall be put to death” is no less usual. This change reflects an evolution from what we might call folk law to a legal system.
42. J.M. KELLY, “The Growth-Pattern of the Praetor’s Edict”, *The Irish Jurist* 1 (1966), p. 354–355; 349.
43. A. WATSON, “The Development of the Praetor’s Edict”, *JRS* 60 (1970), p. 106–107.

D.4.2.9.3 [Ulp. 11 *ad ed.*] or *interdicta* (e.g. *quod vi aut clam*⁴⁴). In this sense, within his model, Watson emphasizes that the injunctions may have been approved from an early date and continued to be approved until the end of the Republic⁴⁵. Following this evolution, it seems that the last republican stage corresponds to a period of greater edictal production, and that for the year 70 BC, a legal corpus that differed from the *ius civile* was being composed⁴⁶. A more complete selection of references in relation to these legal developments is detailed in tables 5 and 6. While it could be that this last Republican stage seems to be more fertile because there is a greater number of references to edicts of this era, it is true that at this time the edict already had a strong influence as a legal source. In fact, Cicero mentions the *ius praetorium* in his *Verrines*, 2.1–2⁴⁷, being that in his treaty *De legibus* (written 30 years later) the author pointed out that many people thought that the praetorian edict had eclipsed the XII tables as a source of law⁴⁸. In fact, some jurists like Servius Sulpicius Rufus or his disciple Ofilius started making comments on the praetorian edict at the end of the Republic⁴⁹.

Personally, I do not find particularly useful to date edicts by considering the language used to phrase legal remedies. Instead, I believe that the elements that help to place this edict over time are the historical context and the evolution of the civil procedure, events that influenced the *ius edicendi*, since Roman law is essentially formed by actions⁵⁰. Therefore, I focus on situations *de facto* occurring

44. Text of the *interdictum* included in D.43.24.1pr. (Ulp. 71 *ad ed.*). For some literature, see I. FARGNOLI, *Studi sulla legittimazione attiva all'interdetto quod vi aut clam*, Milan, 1998. For some other *interdicta*, see G. MANCUSO, “Tra *edictum* e *interdictum*. Appunti su alcune terminologie in tema di testi interdittali”, *IVRA* 42 (1991), p. 110–132.

45. WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 43), p. 109–110.

46. *Edictum de convicio* (*Rhet ad Her.*, 4.25.35); edictal clauses providing *bonorum possessio* for diverse reasons (Cic. *Quint.*, 19.60); *edictum de hominibus armatis coactisve et vi bonorum raptorum* (Cic. *Tul.*, 4.8); *edictum de dolo* (Cic. *De nat. deor.*, 3.30.74); *edictum de pactis* (Cic. *Att.*, 2.9.1). To these sources, and those included in table 6, I must add the mentions to other edicts made by jurists of the Republican era, such as Servius Sulpicius Rufus, who died in 43 BC. (W. KUNKEL, *Herkunft und soziale Stellung der römischen Juristen*, Köln, 2001, p. 25); Trebatius Testa and Ofilius (both from the 1st cent BC.). To consult these mentions, see WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 43), p. 109.

47. A notion that is also mentioned in later authors, such as Papinian (D. 1.1.7) or in the *Historia Augusta*, 13.1.4.

48. Cic. *Leg.*, 1.17.

49. D. 1.2.2.44 (Pomp. Lib. sing. *ench.*). Also mentions that fact R. BAUMAN, *Lawyers in Roman Transitional Politics: A Study of the Roman Jurists in Their Political Setting in the Late Republic and Triumvirate*, Munich, 1985, p. 12–14; T.C. BRENNAN, *The Praetorship in the Roman Republic: 122 to 49 BC.*, New York, 2000, p. 133. Concerning Servius, see J. HARRIES, *Cicero and the Jurists*, Bristol, 2002, p. 116–33 and also “Servius, Cicero and the *Res publica* of Justinian”, in P.J. DU PLESSIS (ed.), *Cicero’s Law: Rethinking Roman Law of the Late Republic*, Edinburgh, 2016, p. 123–144.

50. M. WLASSAK, *Edikt und Klageform. Eine romanistische Studie*, Jena, 1882, p. 120; A.A.V.V., *L’editto del pretore*, in M. TALAMANCA (ed.), *Lineamenti di storia del diritto romano*, Milan, 1989,

at the end of the Republic, and on some provisions that display similar features to the *edictum de naufragio*. In this period, some of the clauses of the edict were maintained from year to year, although the praetors could introduce modifications in these dispositions⁵¹. As has already been mentioned, the social turbulences of the decade between 80–70 BC made violence or *vis*⁵² a recurrent issue in what concerns the repression of delicts⁵³.

Only a few of these edictal dispositions are chronologically dated, such as the *formula Octaviana* (79 BC) or the edict of Lucullus (76 BC), but generally speaking, it is rare for the Republican provisions to have a clear dating⁵⁴. One of these few examples corresponds to the year 79 BC, when the praetor Metellus included the *formula Octaviana* in his edict, this being an action aiming to protect subjects extorted by force or fear⁵⁵. The *formula Octaviana*⁵⁶ influenced the creation of norms in relation to violence, because it had established the basis for the approval of the *quaestio de vi*, through the *lex Lutatia* (78 BC), and probably the *lex Plautia*

p. 147; D. MANTOVANI, “Praetoris partes. La iurisdictio e i suoi vincoli nel processo formulare: un percorso negli studi”, in M.G. DI RENZO VILLATA, *Il diritto fra scoperta e creazione: giudici e giuristi nella storia della giustizia civile; atti del Convegno Internazionale della Società Italiana di storia del diritto*, Napoli, 18–20 ottobre 2001, Naples, 2003, p. 42–43.

51. Cic. *Ver.*, 2.1.44; 2.1.144; C. MOATTI, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 223.
52. For some references concerning violence, see J. COROI, *La violence en droit criminel romain*, Paris, 1915; A.W. LINTOTT, *o.c.* (n. 38); C.J. FUHRMANN, “Vis”, in R. BAGNALL (ed.), *Encyclopaedia of Ancient History*, London/New York, 2012, p. 7015. See also table 6.
53. Violence was a constant theme in Roman law from the archaic period, being integrated into the principle of self-compensation, A.W. LINTOTT, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 6–34; A. RIGGSBY, *o.c.* (n. 38), esp. chap. 4; C.J. FUHRMANN, *Policing the Roman Empire: Soldiers, Administration and Public Order*, Oxford, 2012, p. 49–52; S. GALEOTTI, “L’editto di Lucullo e il processo a C. Antonius Hybrida. Osservazioni in tema di *edictum de vi hominibus armatis coactisve*”, *Rivista di diritto romano* 16–17 (2016–2017), p. 16–17.
54. A. WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 43), p. 105.
55. Cic. *Ver.*, 3. 152; A.W. LINTOTT, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 130; M. BALZARINI, *Ricerche in tema di rapina e di danno violento*, Padova, 1969, p. 144–145; B.W. FRIER, *o.c.* (n. 37), p. 225; K. TUORI, *The Emperor of Law: The Emergence of Roman Imperial Adjudication*, Oxford, 2016, p. 64; J. HAUBENHOFER, “Cogebantur Sullani homines quae per vim et metum abstulerant reddere: Überlegungen zu Cic. *Q.fr.* 1.1.21”, *RIDA* 60 (2013), p. 165; although there are some authors who think that this formula dates from the year 71 BC, see U. VON LÜBTOW, *Der Ediktstittel Quod metus causa gestum erit*, Amsterdam, 1932, p. 126–129; A.S. HARTKAMP, *Der Zwang im römischen Privatrecht*, Las Palmas, 1971, p. 191–193; 245–247.
56. A.F. RUDORFF, “Über die Octavianische Formel”, *ZGRW* 12 (1845), p. 131–170; G. CERVENCA, “Per la storia dell’editto *quod metus causa*”, *SDHI* 31 (1966), p. 312–316; U. EBERT, *Die Geschichte des Edikts de hominibus armatis coactisve*, Heidelberg, 1968, p. 108–109; “*Vi metusve causa*”, *ZSS* 86 (1969), p. 404; B. KUPISCH, “*Quod metus causa gestum erit, ratum non habebit*”, in A. DUFOUR, B. WINIGER (eds.), *Pacte, convention, contrat. Mélanges en l’honneur du professeur Bruno Schmidlin*, Bâle, 1998, p. 471–474; C. VENTURINI, *Metus*, in A. BISCARDI, J. PARICIO (eds.), *Derecho romano de obligaciones. Homenaje al Profesor José Luis Murga Gener*, Madrid, 1994, p. 922–930.; E. CALORE, *Actio quod metus causa. Tutela della vittima e azione in rem scripta*, Milan, 2011, p. 11–21, 125–154.

(78–63 BC⁵⁷). With the *formula Octaviana*, the objective was explicit and political (Cic. Q. Fr., 1.1.21), since the intention was to force Sulla's men to return what they took by extortion. Therefore, this provision was intended to act against a particular concrete situation, and not to create an objective principle of justice. On the other hand, Balzarini⁵⁸ and Maschi⁵⁹ have indicated that this formula was at the same time the origin of the *actio quod metus causa* (of unknown date), and of the edict of Lucullus, which as I shall see a little later, was the origin of the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*.

The *edictum de turba* constitutes another important provision, unfortunately not dated but reconstructed by Lenel as being located next to the *edictum de naufragio* and *de hominibus armatis coactisve et vi bonorum*⁶⁰. In fact, that disposition has similar features to the edict of Lucullus, the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, and with the *actio de naufragio*. The *edictum de turba* was devoted to suppressing violent actions committed taking advantage of a crowd, whether planned beforehand or not, resulting in damage caused to a third party⁶¹. These provisions, as well as the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* and *de naufragio*, are connected to the problem of public order. The violence caused by the crowd may mistakenly lead me to think of a crime, but I must bear in mind that one of the common elements between these provisions is that all these actions are civil, not criminal remedies. For this reason, a compensation is required from offenders, and they were not liable to suffer a penalty from the government⁶².

Sometime during the period 73–71 BC, the praetor Lucius Metelus approved the *interdictum de vi armata*, which belonged to the group of interdicts *unde vi* that were intended to retrieve the property of people who had been deprived of it because of acts implying armed violence⁶³. This source is important in connection with Lucullus' edict (76 BC), and its subsequent evolution into the *actio de hominibus armatis coactisve et ui bonorum*, because this remedy sought to repress behaviour included in Lucullus' edict⁶⁴. The highly procedural and administrative nature of the dispositions show how violence characterized this historical period. So this provision was approved in a way that guaranteed the guardianship of the

57. W. VITZHUM, *Untersuchungen zum materiellen Inhalt der lex Plautia und lex Iulia de vi*, Munich, 1966; B.W. FRIER, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 232; B. SANTALUCIA, *Diritto e processo penale nella antica Roma*, Milan, 1998, p. 155–156.

58. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 142, 150.

59. C.A. MASCHI, *Il diritto romano I. La prospettiva storica della giurisprudenza classica*, Milan, 1966, p. 657.

60. O. LENEL, *EP*³, p. 391–396, § 187–189.

61. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 13.

62. P. BIRKS, *The Roman Law of Obligations*, Oxford, 2014, p. 190.

63. In fact, when we read the *Pro Caecina* of Cicero (Cic. *Caec.*, 41–48, 55, 60–61, 88), it is possible to appreciate that this injunction dates from the year 69 BC.

64. B.W. FRIER, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 237.

property and thus avoided private vengeance, which would have meant a return to legal archaism⁶⁵.

In sum, the years from 80 to 60 BC offer a unique opportunity to observe the urban praetor creating particular provisions designed to repress concrete situations, and allows studying the legal changes of the edict. In this way, the praetor was about to change the background of the law, although how was he doing that is still one topic of discussion⁶⁶. These sources allow me to observe how these forms of repression of violent behaviors are located in a line of action *a minore ad maius*. As can be appreciated in table 5, I propose that the *edictum de naufragio* should have been approved not much later than Lucullus' edict, the *edictum de turba* or the *formula Octaviana*.

Differently, Balzarini⁶⁷ thinks that shipwrecking was penalized through the *lex Iulia de vi*⁶⁸, so that the edict was established after that law was enacted (17 BC). Later, various cases would have been punished *extra ordinem* through imperial provisions such as those included in § 3.8, § 4.1 and § 7 of the Digest' title 47.9. As for the *extra ordinem* repression of the behaviours included in the edict *de naufragio*, while some authors think that it began with Antoninus Pius (§ 4.1)⁶⁹, others attribute this change to Claudius (§ 3.8). As regards the *lex Iulia de vi privata*, Marcianus writes:

D. 48.7.1pr.–2 (Marcianus 14 *inst.*): *De vi privata damnati pars tertia bonorum ex lege Iulia publicatur et cautum est, ne senator sit, ne decurio, aut ullum honorem capiat, neve in eum ordinem sedeat, neve iudex sit: et videlicet omni honore quasi infamis ex senatus consulto carebit. 1. Eadem poena adficiuntur, qui ad poenam legis Iuliae de vi privata rediguntur, et si quis ex naufragio dolo malo quid rapuerit. 2. Sed et ex constitutionibus principum extra ordinem, qui de naufragiis aliquid diriperint, puniuntur: nam et divus Pius rescripsit nullam vim nautis fieri debere et, si quis fecerit, ut severissime puniatur.*

In his study about the *lex Iulia*, Cloud indicates that the penalty for both the *rapina ex naufragio* or *ex incendio*, belongs to the repressive scope of the *edictum de naufragio* and not to the conducts included in the *lex Iulia de vi*⁷⁰. In fact, Marcian's comment seems to point to the fact that the *lex de vi* could include these

65. B. SANTALUCIA, *o.c.* (n. 57), 37–40.

66. T.C. BRENNAN, *o.c.* (n. 49), p. 133, 464. In the late Republic, each praetor had total power to introduce and adapt innovations as he thought necessary, H. DERNBURG, *o.c.* (n. 40), p. 93–132, tried to establish an evolution of the divisible edict into three stages, but his theory was criticized by J.M. KELLY, *o.c.* (n. 42), p. 341–345, who indicated that the creativity of the praetors had a great influence on the evolution of the edict.

67. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 213–215, n. 85.

68. J. COROI, *La violence en droit criminel romain*, Paris, 1915, p. 186.

69. F.M. DE ROBERTIS, "Arbitrium iudicantis e statuizioni imperiali", *ZSS* 59 (1939), p. 238, n. 1.

70. J.D. CLOUD, "Lex Iulia de vi, I", *Athenaeum* 66 (1988), p. 583; ID., "Lex Iulia de vi: part 2", *Athenaeum* 67 (1989), p. 436.

behaviors contained in an edict that, according to my hypothesis, was approved by the praetor more than 50 years before. A similar fact can be observed in the title D.48.6 (*Ad legem Iuliam de vi publica*), specifically in fragment 3pr.–6, texts in which the Severian jurist refers to the assumptions collected in the edict of Lucullus concerning the scope of the *lex de vi*. This is a sign that, in his opinion, these violent behaviours could be collected within the scope of this law, probably to maintain adequate protection as the edicts punishing these behaviours had been in force for a long time. Apart from this, the fact that Marcian mentioned these behaviours implies that the jurist considered them worthy of protection by laws as broad as that of *vis*.

Balzarini, for his part, believes that the presumed inclusion of shipwrecking in the *lex Iulia* precedes the *edictum de naufragio*, which would have been approved immediately afterwards⁷¹. However, the *edictum de naufragio* fits perfectly with the Republican way of creating law, when the praetor's aim was to approve edicts that addressed specific situations. The edict of Lucullus is similar in both its disposition and the associated penalty, and Cicero's mention of *neque incendio neque naufragio* from the *Paradoxa stoicorum* (6.51.8) helps to set a term *ante quem*. According to Vacca, the *lex Iulia* covered some behaviours (such as those associated with the *lex Plautia de vi*), but it does not consider the notion of violence as a material activity aiming to cause harm. This law configures a notion of violence which covers any attitude aimed to paralyze the resistance of the passive subject: violence is therefore inherent to the circumstances when the offence is committed, and not the offence itself⁷². In my opinion, this fragment constitutes a sample of the diversity of procedural sources available to the victim should he or she suffer one of these situations, as mentioned by Ulpian in D.47.8.2.1, and fragment 1 § 1 of the title.

An additional *conundrum* to these considerations would be the aims and purpose of Marcian's institutions. While Pernice believed that this work served as a reader and introductory material for imperial officials, the chancellery or the provinces⁷³, Ferrini understood that it aimed to be a book of introduction to Roman law for the Oriental inhabitants of the Empire, incorporated into Roman citizenship after the *Constitutio Antoniniana* (212)⁷⁴. However, in such a case it is difficult to understand why it was not directly written in Greek⁷⁵. Finally, Schulz considered that there were clear differences among books, so he thought

71. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 215, n. 85.

72. L. VACCA, *Ricerche in tema di actio vi bonorum raptorum*, Milan, 1972, p. 88.

73. A. PERNICE, "Über die sogenannten *res communes omnium*", in *Festgabe der Gießener Juristenfakultät für Heinrich Dernburg zum 4. April 1900*, Berlin, 1900, p. 3–10.

74. C. FERRINI, "Intorno alle Istituzioni di Marciano", in E. ALBERTARIO (ed.), *Opere di Contardo Ferrini 2*, Milan, 1929, p. 287.

75. F.J. ANDRÉS, "Elio Marciano", in R. DOMINGO OSLÉ (ed.), *Juristas Universales: I Juristas antiguos; II Juristas modernos; III Juristas del siglo XIX, y IV Juristas del siglo XX*, Madrid, 2004, p. 132.

that probably it was not conceived at first as a whole, but would be the result of a posthumous publication that incorporated two writings of Marcian with different purposes⁷⁶. This theory does not currently have many followers. These observations are intended to highlight that, with his institutions, Marcian did not intend to establish rigid categories, but rather to comment on and explain the law of his time⁷⁷. Section 4.2 will provide further insights on the relationship between the *edictum de naufragio* and Lucullus' edict. As all these dispositions are responses to crises, violence or force majeure, they are therefore related to situations that caused the need for direct and concrete measures⁷⁸. Later, perhaps with the codification of Hadrian's edict⁷⁹, the trend seems to follow the approval of more general edicts, such as one that covered all forms of robbery such as *vi bonorum raptorum*, *actio de dolo malo*⁸⁰ or *actio de metus*, which included a bigger number of situations *de facto*.

4. The *edictum de naufragio*

4.1. Features

As I indicated earlier, I believe that the *edictum de naufragio* was approved in the last century of the Republic. As for the provision itself, the Digest states:

D.47.9.1pr. (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*) *Praetor ait: In eum, qui ex incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata quid rapuisse recepisse dolo malo damnive quid in his rebus dedisse dicetur: in quadruplum in anno, quo primum de ea re experiundi potestas*

76. F. SCHULZ, *History of Roman Legal Science*, Oxford, 1964, p. 107; 172–176.

77. This constitutes a feature that can be observed in other authors of books of institutions, like Gaius, who gets his system from the dialectic method used by classical Greek authors, as was demonstrated by F. WIEACKER. “Griechische Wurzeln des Institutionensystems”, *ZSS* 70 (1953), p. 93–120, especially 103.

78. B.W. FRIER, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 233.

79. About this codification, the main sources of knowledge are Eutr. 8.17; *Brev.*, lv–lvii; Hieron. 2.167; Aur. Vict. *Caes.*, 19.1–2; Hist. Aug. 1.1; CTh. 11.36.26; CTh. 4.4.7pr.; CTh. 4.5.10.1; thus all of them are postclassic. For different theories about the nature of this edict, see K. TUORI, “Hadrian’s Perpetual Edict: Ancient Sources and Modern Ideals in the Making of a Historical Tradition”, *The Journal of Legal History* 27–3 (2006), p. 219–237; ID., *Ancient Roman lawyers and Modern Legal Ideals. Studies on the Impact of Contemporary Concerns in the Interpretation of Ancient Roman Legal History*, Frankfurt am Main, 2007, p. 136–143, with related bibliography.

80. P. LAMBRINI, “*Actio de dolo malo* e accordi privi di tutela contrattuale”, *Seminarios complutenses de derecho romano: revista complutense de derecho romano y tradición romanística* 22 (2009), p. 239: “l’*actio de dolo malo* sanzionasse qualsiasi condotta connotata da scorrettezza contro la quale il danneggiato non avesse altra tutela. Spesso il dolo si evidenziava soltanto nel momento in cui il soggetto pretendeva di far valere una situazione, la cui applicazione in quel caso concreto si sarebbe rivelata dannosa, e già solo perciò iniqua.”

*fuert, post annum in simplum iudicium dabo. Item in servum et in familiam*⁸¹
*iudicium dabo*⁸².

81. Text preserved in PS. V.3.2 and C. 6.2.18 (294) (see table 6). Lenel did not believe that the phrase *item in servum et in familiam iudicium dabo* was the work of Ulpian or that it belonged to the edict, but that it was an interpolation. Cf. O. LENEL, *Pal. II.* (E. 189), p. 765–6; a sentence also conceived as interpolated by B. BIONDI, “Le *actiones noxales* nel diritto penale classico”, *AUPA* 10 (1925), p. 192. To justify his claim, Lenel referred to the previous title (*vi bonorum raptorum*), and more specifically, to fragment D. 47.8.4.15 (56 Ulp. *Ad ed.*), which could be read in *servum autem et in familiam praetor dat actionem*. The author indicated that this phrase did not seem to come from Ulpian and justified himself by indicating that in that fragment only the possibility of a noxal action was collected, something that is also reflected in the fragment of the edict. Here, Lenel seems to be abusing a systematic conception, having conceived that all actions must possess the same characteristics. Apart from that, if I contrast the fragment with the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, it can be observed that the criminal treatment is similar to that of shipwreck, and that this fragment has not been considered altered by the author, a fact that could question this supposed interpolation. Letizia Vacca compares the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* according to Cicero’s text *Pro Tullio*, in which the speaker mentions the term “family” referring to the edict of Lucullus, while in the edict itself (D. 47.8.2*pr.*) no reference is made to the term, cf. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 91–95. The author justifies that the granting of the *actiones familiae nomine* to the *dominus* are necessary since they are not inherent concepts to one’s own guarantees corresponding to the act of shipwreck, see. P. HUVELIN, *Études sur le furtum dans le très ancien droit romain*, Rome, 1968, p. 120–125. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), indicates that the inclusion of this term resulted in damage to the estate of the convicted person, since he could be liable in the event that an offence was committed by more than one of his subjects. By “family” Lucullus’ edict refers to all dependents, therefore, making present that a responsibility is recognized for guilt in vigilant as can be understood of Cicero according to, L. SOLIDORO, “La familia nell’editto di Lucullo”, *Atti dell’Accademia di scienze morali e politiche* 91 (1981), p. 36–38.
82. Lenel (*EP*³, p. 396) also considered that noxal responsibility did not have to appear expressly, since the praetor did not include this promise in all his actions created by him. See also F. DE VISSCHER, *Le régime romain de la noxalité. De la vengeance collective à la responsabilité individuelle*, Brussels, 1964, p. 17–23; B. BIONDI, *o.c.* (n. 81), p. 11; “Noxa”, in *NDI*, Turin, 1965, p. 449–450. The author based his claim on Gai. 4.76, a fragment in which the act of shipwreck is not mentioned. From my point of view, the list established by Gaius did not have strict character, but in this one mentions were made by way of examples, something characteristic of the didactic character of the work of Gaius; R. QUADRATO, *Gaius dixit. La voce di un giurista di frontiera*, Bari, 2010, p. 1127, and that is observed in the use of the *velut* connector. See P. SOKOŁOWSKI, *Die Philosophie im Privatrecht*, I, Halle, 1902, p. 41; M. KASER, “Gaius und die Klassiker”, *ZSS* 70 (1953), p. 142–146; F. WIEACKER, “Griechische Wurzeln des Institutionensystems”, *ZSS* 70 (1953), p. 93–100; J. STROUX, *Römische Rechtswissenschaft und Rhetorik*, Potsdam, 1949, p. 94–99; H. KRELLER, “Res als Zentralbegriff des Institutionensystems”, *ZSS* 66 (1949), p. 572–580; H. COING, “Zum Einfluß der Philosophie der Aristoteles auf die Entwicklung des römischen Rechts”, *ZSS* 69 (1952), p. 24–29; T. HONORÉ, *Gaius*, Oxford, 1962, p. 18; C. GIOFFREDI, “Aspetti della sistematica gaiana”, in *Nuovi studi di diritto greco e romano*, Rome, 1980, p. 263; O. STANOJEVIC, “Gaius and Pomponius (Notes on David Pugsley)”, *RIDA* 44 (1997), p. 342; J.F. GERKENS, “Gaius, professeur de droit et jurisconsulte”, in *Ad amicissimum amici scripsimus. Vriendenboek Raf Verstegen*, Bruges, 2004, p. 122–125, taking into account the casuistic nature of Roman law, it is possible to understand that Gaius’s statement was classificatory for pedagogical reasons, but it was understood that the possibilities of abstraction and analogy underlay the reading of the commentary. In classical Roman law, *noxae deditio*, was a consequence of the

The *actio de naufragio* was a civil action⁸³, which was addressed to the behaviours of *rapere*, *recipere* and *damnum dare* performed at the same time and in the place where a catastrophe took place (*incendio, ruina, naufragio*⁸⁴). In turn, the edict also applied when these behaviours happened when a ship had been attacked⁸⁵. This confirms the connection of the edict with the practices of the *ius naufragii* and piracy. The PS fragment V.3.2 (from *his quae per turbam fiunt*), also includes the conducts of *suppresserit, celauerit*. In sum, the *actio de naufragio* had the following features: (1) penalty for the fourth of the value of the thing stolen (*in quadruplum*),

personality of the penalty, and it was configured as a type of *vindicatio* of the affected one, a remnant of the old private revenge. In my case, noxality was included in both the edict and the alleged *vi bonorum raptorum*, as an ancient archaic loophole through which one can recognize the evolution that has taken place from the prevailing autocomposition in archaic criminal law to the punitive system that was reflected in the *edictum de naufragio*. Cf. P. DEL PRETE, *La responsabilità dello schiavo nel diritto penale romano*, Roma, 1972, p. 12–29; P. VOICI, “Azioni penali e azioni miste”, *SDHI* 64 (1998), p. 109–117; F. DE VISSCHER, *o.c.* (n. 82), p. 143–146; 208–212. C. SANFILIPPO, *Corso di diritto penale romano, gli atti illeciti. Pena e risarcimento*, Catania, 1960, p. 63; V. ARANGIO-RUIZ, *Istituzioni di diritto romano*, Milan, 1984, p. 160, n. 1; B. BIONDI, *o.c.* (n. 65), p. 1–41; ID., “Problema ed ipotesi in tema di *actiones noxales*”, *BIDR* 36 (1928), p. 99–126; B. SANTALUCIA, “Dalla vendetta alla pena”, in *Storia di Roma* I, Turin, 1988, p. 427–449.

83. Even if some criminal actions admitted to concur with other *actiones reipersecutoriae* for, in addition to criminalize with a sum of money the commission of a crime, as well as pursue the repair of some damage caused in a marriage, see L. VACCA, “Ricerche sulla rapina nel diritto Romano I. L’editto di Lucullo e la *lex Plautia*”, *Studi economico-giuridici dell’università di Cagliari* 45 (1965), p. 560–565; EAD., *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 172–178.; H. ANKUM, “Actions by which we claim a thing (*res*) and a penalty (*poena*) in Classical Roman Law”, *BIDR* 85 (1982), p. 15–20; L. VACCA, “Delitti privati e azioni penali nel principato”, *ANRW* II 14 (1982), p. 682–694; H. ANKUM, “Gaius, Teophilus and Tribonian and the *Actiones mixtae*”, in P. STEIN, P. LEWIS (eds.), *Studies in Justinian’s Institutes in Memory of J.A.C. Thomas*, London, 1983, p. 4–12; L. VACCA, “*Actiones poenales* e *actiones quibus in rem persequimur*”, *IVRA* 40 (1989), p. 41–54; EAD., “Azioni penali ex delicto: pena e reintegrazione patrimoniale”, in O. DILIBERTO (ed.), *Il problema della pena criminale tra filosofia greca e diritto romano: atti del deuxième Colloque de philosophie pénale: Cagliari, 20–22 aprile*, Naples, 1993, p. 197–217; *Delitti privati e azioni penali. Scritti di diritto romano*, Naples, 2015 (volume that includes all Vacca’s articles about criminal law). *Contra*, M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 45, n. 11. Vacca was the greatest follower of this theory, basing her opinion on the texts of Gaius (Gai. 4.6–8) who indicated that in the case of rapine, the restitution of property could be obtained thanks to the *vindicatio*. Gai. 4.8–9 (8. *Poenam tantum persequimur uelut actione furti et iniuriarum et secundum quorundam opinionem actione ui bonorum raptorum; nam ipsius rei et uindicatio et conditio nobis competit*. 9. *Rem uero et poenam persequimur uelut ex his causis, ex quibus aduersus infitiantem in duplum agimus; quod accidit per actionem iudicati, depensi, damni iniuriae legis Aquiliae, aut legatorum nomine, quae per damnationem certa relicta sunt*).
84. D.47.9.1.2–5 (Ulp. 56 *ad edict.*); and D.47.9.2 (Gai. 21 *ad edict. prov.*), this last fragment constitutes a link to relate a fragment with another, which is typical of compilers, cf. T. HONORÉ, *Justinian’s Digest: Character & Compilation*, Oxford, 2010, p. 85–6.
85. O. LENEL, *EP*³, p. 383; D.47.9.3.1. (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*): *deinde ait praetor: “rate, navi expugnata” expugnare videtur, qui in ipso quasi proelio et pugna aduersus navem et ratem aliquid rapit, sive expugnet, sive praedonibus expugnantibus rapiat*.

(2) noxality⁸⁶, (3) cumulative penalty⁸⁷, and (4) passive intransmissibility⁸⁸. The essential element was no longer simply *vis*, but qualified violence, since the actions included in the edict were committed in particular circumstances. This indicates that this action probably belongs chronologically to this period, a provision rooted in a particular historical moment⁸⁹.

The *edictum de naufragio* is located in the title 34 § 189 of the *edictum perpetuum*, classified as *de vi turba incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata*⁹⁰. In fact, Lenel placed the edict under the title *de vi turba incendio*, next to and following the provision § 187 *de hominibus armatis et vi bonorum raptorum* and § 188 *de turba*. In the order of the perpetual edict, this disposition is located after the title *de prediatoribus* and before the title dedicated to the crimes *de iniuriis*. Since the order of the perpetual edict is an order of actions, the determining connections of that order will be precisely those of the actions themselves. This reconstruction of the praetorian edict coincides with the historical context of the end of the Republic, when a series of provisions dealing with violent behaviour were approved⁹¹. The text of the edict mentions three criminal behaviours that shape the case: the *rapina* and the *damnum* committed in the context of catastrophic situations. As I have previously mentioned, a fragment of the *Paradoxa stoicorum ad M. Brutum* (6.51.8) from 46 BC, says *neque incendio neque naufragio*, which could be considered as a *terminus ante quem*⁹². Similarly, the fragment D. 16.3.1.1 (Ulp. 30 *ad ed.*) mentions *neque incendii neque ruinae neque naufragii*. As can be seen in table 4, several texts from different authors connect both events, highlighting that their similarities are not just perceivable in the eyes of the jurists, but also to literary authors such as Seneca. The text corresponds with book 30 of the commentary to the edict and this disposition belongs to book 56. I can see that the praetor already considered these terms together even before approving the *edictum de naufragio*.

The *edictum de naufragio* constituted an autonomous kind of *furtum*⁹³, included in a praetor's edict dealing with particular cases, a typical feature of the

86. D. 47.9.1pr. (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*) *in fine*.

87. D. 47.9.1.1 (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*).

88. D. 47.9.4.2 (Paul 54 *ad ed.*).

89. Similarly, Vacca qualified the penalized behavior reflected in the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* (D. 47.8), as a case of robbery qualified with violence, which provoked the concurrence of criminal actions with re-persecutory means, L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 83), p. 545–546, 562–565.

90. O. LENEL, *EP*³, p. 396–397.

91. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 83), p. 562; L. LABRUNA, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 33ss.; *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 525–538.

92. See table 6.

93. The dominant doctrine relates the *furtum* and the *rapina*, although this last behaviour constituted a typical case separated by the edict of the praetor approved in the 1st cent. BC, G. DIRKSEN, *Übersicht der bisherigen Versuche zur Kritik und Herstellung des Textes der Zwölf Tafelnfragmente*, Leipzig, 1824, p. 592; F.P. GULLI, “Del furto manifesto nel diritto romano”, *AG* 25 (1880), p. 46–87; Th. MOMMSEN, *Romisches Strafrecht*, Leipzig, 1899, p. 381; O. KARLOWA, *Romische Rechtsgeschichte*, Leipzig, 1901, p. 409; C. FERRINI, “Esposizione storica et dottrinale del diritto

praetorian edicts of the end of the republic⁹⁴. *Rapina* constituted a form of robbery qualified by the use of *vis*⁹⁵ that in this case would take place in catastrophic circumstances. In the edict, as *rapina* is characterized as being committed in catastrophic situations, it should be differentiated from the conducts of *vis* and *rapina* provided in the *edictum de vi bonorum raptorum*⁹⁶.

According to the edict, the behavior of *recipere* should be committed with *dolus malus*, as explained by Ulpian in D. 47.9.3.3⁹⁷, indicating that someone who receives something from a shipwreck does not necessarily have wrongful intent. For that reason, the praetor would have decided to qualify *recipere* with *dolus malus* because that behaviour does not include this feature *per se*⁹⁸. On the contrary,

penale romano”, in *Enciclopedia del Diritto Penale Italiano*, Milan, 1904, p. 228; U. BRASIELLO, “*Rapina*”, in *NDI*, 1939, p. 1073–1075; B. ALBANESE, “La nozione del furto fino a Nerazio”, *AUPA* 23 (1953), p. 42; L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 83), p. 545; EAD., *o.c.* (n. 32), p. 77; M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 395; M.A. FENOCCHIO, *Sulle tracce del delitto di furtum. Genesi sviluppi vicende*, Turin, 2008, p. 192; face to authors who talk about aquilian damage, P. HUVELIN, *o.c.* (n. 64), p. 804 or of *iniuria*, according, ID., “La notion de l’*iniuria* dans le très ancien droit romain”, in *Mélanges Ch. Appleton*, Lyon/Paris, 1903, p. 468; M. KASER, “Neue Studien zum altrömischen Eigentum”, *ZSS* 68–1 (1951), p. 183. Differently, O. BEHREND, “Gesetz und Sprache. Das römische Gesetz unter dem Einfluß der hellenistischen Philosophie”, in O. BEHREND, W. SELLERT (eds.), *Nomos und Gesetz. Ursprünge und Wirkungen des griechischen Gesetzesdenkens. VI Symposium der Kommission “Die Funktion des Gesetzes in Geschichte und Gegenwart”*, Göttingen, 1995, p. 225–228, who thinks that this edict was approved because of a legal void because in the 1st cent. BC *furtum* was conceived as *rem clam amovere*.

94. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 97–103, see also table 6.
95. D. 47.9.3.5 (Ulp. 56 *ad edict.*): *Aliud esse autem rapi, aliud amoveri palam est, si quidem amoveri aliquid etiam sine vi possit: rapi autem sine vi non potest*. In this sense, the relationship between *vis* and *rapina* was complicated because *vis* was a crime in itself, but in turn qualified the *rapina*, establishing its differentiation from *furtum*. See O. ROBINSON, *The Criminal Law of Ancient Rome*, Baltimore, 1995, p. 29; J. HARRIES, *Law and crime in the Roman world*, Cambridge, 2007, p. 106–117; P. BIRKS, *The Roman law of Obligations*, Oxford, 2014, p. 189. For more general notions of the concept of violence, see “*Vis*”, in *VIR*, vol. 5, Berlin, 1939, p. 1404–1407; G. LONGO, “*Vis*”, in *NDI* 20, Turin, 1957, p. 988–994; C.J. FUHRMANN, “*Vis, Violentia*”, in R. BAGNALL (ed.), *The Encyclopedia of Ancient History*, New York/London, 2012, p. 7015–7016; S. HORNBLOWER, A. SPAWFORTH (eds.), “*Vis*”, in *OCD*, Oxford, 2012, p. 1560–1561.
96. O. ROBINSON, *o.c.* (n. 95), p. 35.
97. D. 47.9.3.3 (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*): *Sed enim additum est “dolo malo”, quia non omnis qui recipit statim etiam delinquit, sed qui dolo malo recipit*. Fragment considered interpolated as F. DE MARTINO, “In tema di stato i necessità”, *RISG* 14 (1939), p. 44–45; B. BEINART, “The relationship of *iniuria* and *culpa* in the *lex Aquilia*”, in *Studi in onore di Vincenzo Arangio Ruiz I*, Naples, 1952, p. 287 n. 3; G. LONGO, “Sulla legittima difesa e sullo stato di necessità in Diritto Romano”, in *Sein und Werden im Recht, Festgabe von Lütbow*, Berlin, 1970, p. 334–435; S. SCHIPANI, *Responsabilità ex lege Aquilia. Criteri di imputazioni e problema della culpa*, Turin, 1969, p. 207; contra: J.F. GERKENS, *Aequae perituris...: Une approche de la causalité dépassante en droit romain classique*, Liège, 1997, p. 102, indicating that it is strange that the compilers wanted to modify the fragment to provoke controversy among jurists of the same school.
98. An opinion shared by A. VON THUR, *Der Nothstand im Civilrecht*, Heidelberg, 1888, p. 64–68; J.F. GERKENS, “État de nécessité et *damnum incendi causa datum*”, *RIDA* 44 (1997),

damnum dare was not connected with bad intent, although from fragment 3.7 I can get that Ulpian considered that the damage should have been committed intending to differentiate it from the behaviour foreseen by the *lex Aquilia*. Labeo, however, indicates that the *actio de naufragio* (in this case, in relation to fire) would be guaranteed, even if there was no fraud. The jurists think differently about this fragment, based on their conception of the catastrophic circumstances (fire, shipwreck) that surround the event in a subjective or objective way⁹⁹. Labeo did not conceive the need for *dolus malus* because at his time, it was not necessary to ensure that the action was guaranteed, following the *lex Aquilia*¹⁰⁰. By introducing this subjective evaluation of the cases, Ulpian needed to indicate that this action should include *dolus malus*¹⁰¹.

Ulpian's comment indicates that the edict was very useful in avoiding false wrecks¹⁰², a practice carried out in maritime transport by shipowners who were transporting goods for the *annona*. This was a usual practice, at least in Claudius's time, and is reflected in Ulpian's comment¹⁰³. As Suetonius tells us, the emperor Claudius experienced hard times of famine, so he stimulated the maritime transport

p. 144; ID., *L'actio de incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata (D.47.9)*, *Seminario internazionale di diritto romano di Soverato*, 2007, p. 18. Also, this opinion is confirmed by various fragments, such as: D. 13.1.14 (Iul. 22 *dig.*) ou D. 4.9.5 (G. *ad ed. prov.*).

99. J.F. GERKENS, "Vis maior and vis cui resisti non potest", in *Ex iusta causa traditur, Essays in Honour of Eric H. Pool*, Pretoria, 2005, p. 109–120, describes the distinction as subjective and objective. Before him, T. MAYER-MALY, "Höhere Gewalt: Falltypen und Begriffsbildung", in *Festschrift Arthur Steinwenter*, Graz, 1958, p. 63; W. ERNST, "Wandlungen des vis maior-Begriffes in der Entwicklung der römischen Rechtswissenschaft", *Index* 22 (1994), p. 293–298, they established differences between cases affected by the *vis maior*. The subjective view understands that the circumstances of the case could justify the conduct of the actor, because of the exceptional situation, as Ulpian established in this passage and also in D. 9.2.15.1 (Ulp. 18 *ad ed.*), Paulo (mentioning a rescript from Antoninus Pius: D. 47.9.4.1 [Paul. 54 *ad ed.*]) and also in Celsus, D. 9.2.49.1 (Ulp. 9 *disp.*) and D. 43.24.7.4 (Ulp. 71 *ad ed.*); Iavolenus, D. 19.2.59 (Iav. 5 *Lab. Post.*) and Gai. 3.211. In addition, the objective view understands that the superior force does not exclude the responsibility of the actor, as in the fragment of Labeo (D. 4.9.3*pr.*), see also D. 43.24.7.4 (Ulp. 71 *ad ed.*).
100. J.F. GERKENS, *o.c.* (n. 98), p. 117; C. GIOFFREDI, "Sull'elemento intenzionale nel diritto penale romano", in *Studi Grosso* III, Turin, 1970, p. 45: "col diritto classico, la valutazione dell'elemento psicologico è acquisita."
101. T. HONORÉ, *o.c.* (n. 13), p. 47ss. and 64, indicating that in his writings, Ulpian mentioned more his opinion than the law *per se*.
102. D. 4.9.1.1. (Ulp. 14 *ad ed.*): *Maxima utilitas est huius edicti, quia necesse est plerumque eorum fidem sequi et res custodiae eorum committere. Ne quisquam putet graviter hoc adversus eos constitutum: nam est in ipsorum arbitrio, ne quem recipiant, et nisi hoc esset statutum, materia daretur cum furibus adversus eos quos recipiunt coeundi, cum ne nunc quidem abstineant huiusmodi fraudibus.*
103. D. 47.9.3.8 (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*). There are also some late texts that reflect the concerns about the person held liable for a shipwreck involving ships linked with public supply, see CTh. 13.9.4; C. 11.6.3; C. 11.6.5.

of grain to Rome, as well as guaranting privileges for sailors and shipowners, and taking charge of costs and responsibilities¹⁰⁴.

The extensive interpretation of Ulpian continues in § 4, in which the jurist included among the repressed conducts in the typical assumption of the edict those of *abstulere* and *amovere*. This extensive interpretation has been qualified as interpolation by Lenel, together with § 5–6¹⁰⁵. To justify the existence of the alteration, Lenel indicated that it was strange to him that after § 3.3, where *dolus malus* was introduced and explained, and before § 3.7 where he commented *damnive quid dedisse*, Ulpian would have introduced § 4–6¹⁰⁶.

104. Suet. *Claud.*, 18.2–19.1; A.J.B. SIRKS, “A favour to rich freed women (*libertinae*) in 51 AD. On Suet. *Claud.*, 19 and the *lex Papia*”, *RIDA* 27 (1980), p. 283–294; W. BROEKAERT, “Roman economic policies during the third century AD: the evidence of the *tituli picti* on oil amphorae”, *Ancient Society* 28 (2008), p. 212–213. In addition, the work of the Emperor on developing Rome’s port is well known, cf. <http://www.portusproject.org/>.

105. O. LENEL, *EP*³, p. 396, § 189; *contra*: O. KARLOWA, *Römische Rechtsgeschichte: Privatrecht und Civilprozess*, Leipzig, 1901, p. 1344–1350.

106. 4. *Non solum autem qui rapuit, sed et qui abstulit vel amovit vel damnum dedit vel recepit, hac actione tenetur*. 5. *Aliud esse autem rapi, aliud amoveri palam est, si quidem amoveri aliquid etiam sine vi possit: rapi autem sine vi non potest*. 6. *Qui eiecta nave quid rapuit, hoc edicto tenetur*. “*Eiecta*” hoc est quod Graeci aiunt ἐξεβράσθη (*eiectum est*). Lenel believes that it is illogical for Ulpian to reintroduce an explanatory comment in § 4 when he had already explained *recepisse dolo malo* extensively in § 3. In Lenel’s justification, it may have had an influence that in § 3.3, Ulpian introduced the notion of *dolo malo*, and did not mention it again until fr. 3 § 7. Again, it seems that the author is falling into an abuse of the systematic conception, so he believes that the commentary on the edict must follow a certain pattern. For this reason, Lenel believes that this fragment belongs to the comment of the formula, not the edict. For his part, M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 465, also believed in the supposed interpolation of § 4–5, justifying it in accordance with the fact that while Ulpian, in § 4, was dealing in parallel with *rapere*, *auferre* and *amovere*, in § 5 he was simply engaged in differentiating between *rapi* and *amoveri*. I do not think that Ulpian omitting *auferre* in § 5 was a sign indicating a possible interpolation, rather I believe that § 4 uses the perfect because the verb is directed towards the subject, whereas § 5 refers to the object, this is clearly seen in the fact that Ulpian uses in § 4 *qui*, while in § 5 he uses *quidem amoveri aliquid*. Let me also bear in mind that the author says *vel abstulit, vel amovit, vel damnum dedit*, and joining the elements of his sentence with disjunctive conjunctions, so they do not have a sense of the whole, but each one is an independent particle that could be used or not according to the assumption of greater or lesser importance. According to L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 103, Ulpian’s speech appeared as sufficiently unitary, since in § 3 the jurist was concerned to identify the scope of the case provided in the edict, treating the subtraction, so it could be understood that it did not end in § 3.3, but continued in the following paragraphs., A.D. MANFREDINI, “Una questione in materia di naufragio”, in *Sodalitas. Studi in onore di A. Guarino*, vol. 5, Naples, 1984, p. 2209–2215 has the same opinion. Both *abstulere* (D. 47.2.21pr.; D. 47.2.21, 10; D. 47.2.46; D. 47.2.48; D. 48.13.4pr.–1) and *amovere* (D. 47.2.4.2; D. 47.2.27.3) are behaviours included in *furtum*, as can be seen in Paul’s classic definition that included the *contrectatio* (D. 47.2.1.3), in which these behaviours were included in *rapina* since they had been carried out with violence (D. 47.9.3.5; D. 47.9.5; D. 47.1.2.1–2). Seeing that violence was inherent in the notion of *rapere*, Ulpian’s comment could be to characterize it to distinguish it from the *furtum* and expose what action was exercisable. Gaius did this in D. 47.9.5 (Gaius 21 *ad ed. Prov.*), differentiating between *furtum* and *rapina* in relation to the

In a 2007's communication, Gerkens¹⁰⁷ asserted that § 8¹⁰⁸, § 9¹⁰⁹, § 10¹¹⁰, § 11¹¹¹ and § 12.1–2¹¹², referring to the cases of the shipwrecker and the arsonist who committed damage on the property of a third party, did not fit among the behaviours described in the edict and that had been included in the title by association of ideas. Gerkens states: “*Nous savons bien sûr qu'en droit postclassique, les actions ont perdu une bonne partie de leur individualité. À l'instar du furtum, nous savons aussi que les délits les plus graves étaient souvent poursuivis exclusivement sur base d'une procédure criminelle. Dès lors, il n'a peut-être pas paru illogique aux compilateurs de compléter par ces deux textes les renseignements disponibles quant à l'incendie*”¹¹³. I mostly agree with his reasoning, but on the other hand, it should be observed how Ulpian (D. 47.9.1.1) mentioned the possibility of using either a civil or a criminal procedure. By mentioning both actions I must appreciate that when Ulpian wrote this comment there were other *extra ordinem* procedural ways to repress the behaviours included in the edict¹¹⁴. Ulpian's phrase reflects the evolution of the Roman procedure, which was gradually absorbed by the *cognitio extra ordinem*, although elements of the *ordo* still persisted in some cases, even in the

violence used, and if the abduction had been committed at a time subsequent to the calamity, when the objects had been stolen. See D. 47.9.1.2–5 (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*), and L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 102–105. Otherwise, M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 466, who thinks that *vis* was not part of *rapina per se*. *Contra*, H. NIEDERMAYER, “*Crimen plagi und crimen violentiae*”, in *Studi in onore di Pietro Bonfante nel XL anno d'insegnamento*, II, Milan, 1930, p. 402, n. 77.

107. J.F. GERKENS, *o.c.* (n. 98), p. 5–9.

108. D. 47.9.8 (Neratius 2 *resp.*): *Ratis vi fluminis in agrum meum delatae non aliter potestatem tibi faciendam, quam si de praeterito quoque damno mihi cavisses.*

109. D. 47.9.9 (Gaius 4 *ad legem duodecim tabularum*): *Qui aedes acervumve frumenti iuxta domum positum conbusserit, vincus verberatus igni necari iubetur, si modo sciens prudensque id commiserit. Si vero casu, id est negligentia, aut noxiam sarcire iubetur aut, si minus idoneus sit, levius castigatur. Appellatione autem aedium omnes species aedificii continentur.*

110. D. 47.9.10 (Ulpianus 1 *op.*): *Ne piscatores nocte lumine ostenso fallant navigantes, quasi in portum aliquem delaturi, eoque modo in periculum naves et qui in eis sunt deducant sibi que execrandam praedam parent, praesidis provinciae religiosa constantia efficiat.*

111. D. 47.9.11 (Marcianus 14 *inst.*): *Si fortuito incendium factum sit, venia indiget, nisi tam lata culpa fuit, ut luxuria aut dolo sit proxima.*

112. D. 47.9.12 (Ulpianus 8 *de officio proconsulis*): *pr. Licere unicuique naufragium suum impune colligere constat: idque imperator Antoninus cum divo patre suo rescripsit. 1. Qui data opera in civitate incendium fecerint, si humiliore loco sint, bestiis obici solent: si in aliquo gradu id fecerint, capite puniuntur aut certe in insulam deportantur.*

113. J.F. GERKENS, *o.c.* (n. 98), p. 6.

114. Something that also prevailed in the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*; L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 83), p. 521–529.; *Id.*, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 6–7; M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 54), p. 40, n. 8; p. 220–221.

provinces¹¹⁵. This fact can be observed in the Digest's title (§ 3.8; 4.1; 7; 12.1) and in other related provisions, such as those shown in table 4, *inter alia*¹¹⁶.

Besides, concerning the assertion about the loss of individuality in crimes in the postclassic era, it is necessary to consider various events on a case-by-case basis. The shipwrecker's episode points to the fact that the edict was not just dealing with shipwrecking practices, but also with other catastrophic situations such as fire or collapse. Fragment PS. V.3.2 belongs to the title *de his quae per turbam fiunt*, for which the catastrophic character of these behaviours was emphasized, but not just focusing on the concrete case of shipwreck. In addition, the title 11.6 of the *Codex Iustinianus* is also devoted to shipwrecking. Therefore, the development of repression measures for shipwrecking since the Republic, and throughout the classic and postclassic era, should be studied in detail and on a case-by-case basis, since the other assumptions collected in the edict had different developments¹¹⁷.

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115. One of the most famous is the case of Babatha's dossier, which focuses on the discovery of an insertion in a papyrus (P. Yadin 12, l. 7) found in a cave in the Judean desert, of a phrase in Greek that corresponded with the *formulae* conceived for the Roman process. Finding a *formula* in a province does not imply that the *ordo iudiciorum publicorum* was applied to it, but that it was an *extra ordinem* procedure for which they have used an *ordo formula*. In this case it seems that the referral of the case to the Roman courts was the initiative of the interested parties. A. BISCARDI, "Nuove testimonianze di un papiro arabo-giudaico per la storia del processo provinciale romano", in *Studi in onore di Gaetano Scherillo*, Milan, 1970, p. 1–41; H. COTTON, "The Guardianship of Jesus Son of Babatha: Roman and Local Law in the Province of Arabia", *JRS* 83 (1999), p. 393–420; "Subscriptions and Signatures in the Papyri from the Judean Desert: The Χειροθήκη", *Journal of Juristic Papyrology* 25 (1995), p. 29–40; "The Guardian (*epitropos*) of a Woman in the Documents from the Judean Desert", *ZPE* 118 (1996), p. 267–273; T. ILAN, "Women's Archives in the Judean Desert", in L. SCHIFFMAN, E. TOV, J. VANDERKAM (eds.), *The Dead Sea Scrolls: Fifty Years after their Discovery 1947–1997*, Jerusalem, 2000; T. CHIUSI, "Babatha vs. The Guardians of her Son: a Struggle for Guardianship-Legal and Practical Aspects of P. Yadin 12–15, 27", in R. KATZOFF, D. SCHAPS, *Law in the Documents of the Judean Desert*, (*Suppl. the Journal of the Study of Judaism* 96), Leiden, 2005, p. 105–132; K. CZAJKOWSKI, *Localized law. The Babatha and Salome Komaise archives*, Oxford, 2017, p. 17–21. Other documents, which deal with the dichotomy existent between *ordo* and *cognitio*, are the *Tabula Contrebiensis*, cf. J.S. RICHARDSON, "The *Tabula Contrebiensis*: Roman Law in Spain in the Early First Century BC", *JRS* 73 (1983), p. 33–41; P. BIRKS, A. RODGER, J.S. RICHARDSON, "Further aspects of the *Tabula Contrebiensis*", *JRS* 74 (1984), p. 45–73; or the *Formula Baetica* (*CIL* II 5042 = *CIL* II 5406), A. D'ORS, *Epigrafia jurídica de la España romana*, Madrid, 1953, p. 431–446, dating the tablet to the 1st cent. AD. This confirms the theory that it is a tablet that was hung as a formula, but also that it was inspired by a real document, probably waxed tablets that were transported from Italy to Baetica, where it was copied.
116. D. 48.7.1.2. (Marc. 14 *inst*): *Sed et ex constitutionibus principum extra ordinem, qui de naufragiis aliquid diriperint, puniuntur: nam et divus Pius rescripsit nullam vim nautis fieri debere et, si quis fecerit, ut severissime puniatur.*
117. L. MINIERI, *Exurere adurere incendere. Studi sul procurato de incendio in diritto romano*, Naples, 2012, p. 90–94, which indicates that arson was not recognized as an individual crime until a title dedicated to this assumption is established in the *Pauli Sententiae* (fr. 5.20). Previously, the only mention to that assumption was located in this edict, in relation with the cases of shipwreck, collapse or assaulted ships.

Penalties for arsonists were similar to the shipwreckers', because the provocation of a fire could also imply *rapina*¹¹⁸. In addition, the quoted fragments compose the typical situation focused on the edict, with the exception of § 8¹¹⁹. The latter established the obligation to repair damage caused unintentionally, something reminiscent from the provisions of the *lex Aquilia*¹²⁰, and in this case, I believe that the compilers associated the other fragments to the issue of the ownership of the goods remaining from the wreckage¹²¹. However, § 9, § 11 and § 12.2 defined and described the different situations of arsoning, and established a distinction between fortuitous situations and those committed with *culpa*¹²². Finally, § 12.2 (= *Coll.* 12.5.1–2) referred to the criminalization of subjects for starting a fire, which, as was usual in postclassical provisions, was graduated according to the social status of the offender (= § 4.1)¹²³.

Another argument would be that § 3.1 and § 10 refer to the provocation of a shipwreck. I should think about the archaic conception of *ius naufragii*, and how the Romans changed that conception, punishing shipwreckers as in § 10¹²⁴. So, it

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118. D. 48.19.28.18 (Call. 6 *de cogn.*); PS. V.20.1; see also B. SITEK, "Criminal liability *incendiarii* in ancient Roman law", *Diritto@storia* 6 (2007), sect. 3.2; L. MINIERI, *o.c.* (n. 117), p. 6, 95.
119. This fragment that belongs to the *libri responsorum* of Neratius has been deemed as authentic by V. SCARANO USSANI, *Valori e storia nella cultura giuridica fra Nerva e Adriano. Studi su Nerazio e Celso*, Naples, 1979, p. 7–8, n. 4; R. GREINER, *Opera Neratii, Drei Textgeschichten*, Karlsruhe, 1973, p. 22–26; F. BONA, "Recensione a Grainer. *Opera Neratii*", *SDHI* 40 (1974), p. 507ss.; these authors indicate that the *libri responsorum* had not been written by Neratius, but that they were probably compiled *a posteriori*, although respecting its original content. One indication could be that, apart from this fragment, there were two other fragments related to *ratis vi fluminis dans agrum alterius delata*, such as D. 10.4.5.4 (Ulp. 24 *ad ed.*); and D. 39.2.9.3 (Ulp. 53 *ad ed.*). Contrary to the opinion of this fragment from book 39 of the Digest, it seems possible to deduce that § 8 was the work of Neratius, seeing that even Ulpian indicated *Neratius autem scribit*.
120. Chapter dealing with objective liability, see D. DAUBE, "On the Third Chapter of the *Lex Aquilia*", *Law Quarterly Review* 52 (1936), p. 253; G. MACCORMACK, "On the Third Chapter of the *Lex Aquilia*", *The Irish Jurist* 5 (1970), p. 164–178; P. PASCHALIDIS, "What did *iniuria* in the *Lex Aquilia* actually mean?", *RIDA* 60 (2008), p. 321–363.
121. The § 6; 4.1; 5; 7; 12*pr.* establishes a similar treatment.
122. O. MILELLI, "Testimonianze Liviane sulla repressione penale dell'incendio", in *Studi in onore Cesare Sanfilippo* vol. 3, Milan, 1983, p. 485; J.F. GERKENS, "État de nécessité et *damnum incendii arcendi causa datum*", *RIDA* 44 (1997), p. 127–129.
123. The penalty is described in G. ALFOLDY, *Römische Sozialgeschichte*, Wiesbaden, 1984, p. 147; 215; R. RILINGER, *Humiliores-Honestiores: zu einer sozialen Dichotomie im Strafrecht der römischen Kaiserzeit*, Munich, 1988, p. 34–38; M. BALZARINI, "Nuove prospettive sulla dicotomia *honestiores-humiliores*", in *Idee vecchie e nuove sul diritto criminale romano*, Padova, 1988, p. 159; 169. Otherwise, G. MACCORMACK, "Criminal liability for fire in early and classical Roman law", *Index* 3 (1972), p. 386; L. MINIERI, *o.c.* (n. 116), p. 90, that indicate that the punishment established in these cases was similar to the *lex Cornelia de sicariis*.
124. Pirate-fishermen are mentioned in Eur. *Hel.*, 766–769; *Iphig. Aul.*, 198; Apollod. *Epit.*, 6, 7–8G; *Juv. Sat.*, 4, 45–52, G. FAGAN, "Violence in social relations", in M. PEACHIN (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Social Relations*, Oxford, 2011, p. 477.

is possible to appreciate how criminal behavior does not only include theft committed on the occasion of shipwreck, but also the provocation of the shipwreck (or fire) that was aimed at committing robbery and perhaps to take those captured as slaves. On the other hand, it is true that § 3.8 and § 10 refer to the sanction of the shipwreck by means other than the act of shipwreck, being the *lex Cornelia de sicariis* (§ 3.8) or the *extra ordinem* resource itself to the imperial magistrate (§ 10), which makes us think that the case of the shipwreck can be penalized in different ways. Be this as may, § 3.1, as well as § 3.4 seem to include it in its repressive *spectrum*, apart from the fact that as can be seen throughout the following chapters, the behaviors included in the shipwreck are penalized differently in different periods. Further, the text of the edict mentions *nave expugnata*, which according to Callistratus in § 6¹²⁵ referred to the case in which the ship was attacked, or if some actions intending to wreck the ship were carried out. In sum, the main features of this edict are the existence of a situation of danger, confusion or catastrophe, and theft committed during these situations, and therefore involving violence *per se*.

The date of approval of the *edictum de naufragio* is quite uncertain, and so its chronological frame needs to be ascertained through other provisions. In the same way, I am not sure if this edict could have been approved in the provinces and then included in the *album* of the urban *praetor*, but it is necessary to mention this in order to consider all possibilities about this provision. Otherwise, the edict of Lucullus was a provincial norm approved by the *praetor peregrinus*, although it became part of the *album praetorio* in more or less 7 years¹²⁶. The edict *de hominibus armatis coactisve et vi bonorum raptorum* was introduced by the praetor Lucullus in 76 BC¹²⁷. Lucullus was a *praetor peregrinus*, but this fact does not prevent me thinking that this edict could have been already incorporated into the edictal album back in 69 BC, a date which corresponds to the speech of Cicero *Pro Tullio* and in which he mentions it¹²⁸. Although during the period when I place the *edictum de naufragio* (1st cent. BC)¹²⁹ both praetors approved independent edicts; I do not have many details to understand with certainty what the relationship was between

125. D.47.9.6. (Callistratus libro primo edicti monitorii): *Expugnatur navis, cum spoliatur aut mergitur aut dissolvitur aut pertunditur aut funes eius praeciduntur aut vela conscinduntur aut anchorae involantur de mare.*

126. Cic. *Tull.*, 7; J.M. KELLY, *Roman Litigation*, Oxford, 1966, p. 15–16; A. WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 65–67; B. FRIER, *o.c.* (n. 38), p. 52–57. G. MANCUSO, “*Praetoris edicta*. Riflessioni terminologiche e spunti per la ricostruzione dell’attività editale del pretore in età repubblicana”, *AUPA* 38 (1983), p. 384, denies the existence of the *album praetorio*, indicating that in fact the praetor approved several edicts during his charge.

127. Asconius, 75. However, S. GALEOTTI, *o.c.* (n. 53), p. 1–19 thinks that in Asconius’ comment on the trial of C. Antonius Hybrida (l. 13ss.) it is possible to appreciate the origin of that action.

128. Cic. *Tull.*, 3.7.

129. R. MARTINI, *Ricerche in tema di editto provinciale*, Milan, 1969, p. 33–38; T.C. BRENNAN, *o.c.* (n. 49), p. 463; A. TORRENT, “El título de *publicanis* y el *genus provinciale* (Cic. *Att.*, 6.1.15). Reflexiones sobre el *edictum provinciale*”, *Rivista di Diritto romano* 14 (2014), p. 298–299.

them¹³⁰. Shipwrecking seem to have been mostly practiced in the provinces, what makes us think about the possible provincial character of this edict. Besides, a preliminary examination of title 47.9 reveals the existence of several fragments from books devoted to provincial law, or mentioning provincial practices (§ 5, § 10 and § 11). Despite that, the presence of these fragments may have been a simple choice by the compilers, including many texts referring to shipwrecking. However, the mention of *naufragio* beside *incendio* and *ruina* indicates that, more than describing events that happened in the provinces (as the case of the provocation of shipwreck mentioned in § 10), the praetor was gathering cases that implied *vis maior*. The latter can be appreciated in D. 44.7.1.4 (Gaius 2 *aur.*). In sum, even it is necessary to mention the possibility that the *edictum de naufragio* was approved in the provinces, the evidence is so scarce that this idea has to be labelled as a hypothesis by now.

4.2. *Actio de naufragio* vs. *Actiones vi bonorum raptorum et de turba*

These features of the *actio de naufragio* link this disposition with two other edicts compiled in the previous title of the Digest (*vi bonorum raptorum* and *de turba*, tit. 47.8). The edicts *vi bonorum raptorum* and *de turba* are part of the same title in Lenel's reconstruction (XXIV), although they are two different edicts¹³¹. Furthermore, as can be seen in the Digest and in Lenel's palingenesia, the comments on these three different edicts belong to the same books written by Ulpian (l. 56) and Paul (l. 54). This is another example of the vicinity of these edicts in the perpetual edict of Julian¹³², since Paul's work influenced that of Ulpian¹³³. Apart from that, the comparison of the content of the fragments indicates a closeness:

130. The competence of the peregrine praetor to approve edicts was mentioned in the *lex Rubria de Gallia Cisalpina* (col. 1, l. 23–25): *Q. Licinium damni infecti... eam stipulationem quam is quei Romae inter peregrinos ius decit in albo propositam habet, L.v Seio repromeississet*. See M. CRAWFORD, *Roman Statutes*, London, 1996, p. 461.

131. O. LENEL, *EP*³, p. 391–397, § 187 (*de homonibus armatis coactisve et vi bonorum raptorum*); § 188 (*de turba*); § 189 (*de incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata*).

132. Comparing several edictal comments, C. GIACHI, "Storia dell'editto e struttura del processo in età pre-adrianea. Un'ipotesi di lavoro", in *Atti del Convegno Processo civile e proceso penale nell'esperienza giuridica del mondo antico*, Siena, 2001, p. 120–121; *Studi su Sesto Pedio: la tradizione, l'editto*, Milan, 2005, p. 3, confirms the order of Julian's edict in the edictal comments of these Severan jurists. A. TORRENT, "La *ordinatio edicti* en la política jurídica de Adriano", *BIDR* 25 (1984), p. 42–43: "*Desgraciadamente no conocemos bien los comentarios al edicto anteriores a la oratio Hadriani, los de Servio Sulpicio, Labeon, Fablo Mela, Sexto Pedio, Viviano, pero todo hace pensar que las divergencias con el edicto adrianeo no debían ser notables, como tampoco son tan grandes las divergencias sistemáticas posteriores porque en todos los comentarios post-adrianeos hay un núcleo de vecindad temática innegable, aunque algunas materias estén desplazadas de sus rúbricas por así decir tradicionales (en la ordenación de Lenel) en la sistemática juliana.*"

133. A.M. HONORÉ, *o.c.* (n. 13), p. 223, citing other authors is more typical of Ulpian than of Paul, which is why Ulpian is more likely to have copied Paul.

D.47.8.2pr. Ulpianus libro 56 ad ed. Praetor ait: “Si cui dolo malo hominibus coactis damni quid factum esse dicetur sive cuius bona rapta esse dicentur, in eum, qui id fecisse dicetur, iudicium dabo. Item si servus fecisse dicetur, in dominum iudicium noxale dabo”.

D.47.8.4pr. Ulpianus libro 56 ad ed. Praetor ait: “Cuius dolo malo in turba damnum quid factum esse dicetur, in eum in anno, quo primum de ea re experiundi potestas fuerit, in duplum, post annum in simplum iudicium dabo.”

D.47.9.1pr. Ulpianus libro 56 ad ed. Praetor ait: “In eum, qui ex incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata quid rapuisse recepit dolo malo damnive quid in his rebus dedisse dicetur: in quadruplum in anno, quo primum de ea re experiundi potestas fuerit, post annum in simplum iudicium dabo. Item in servum et in familiam iudicium dabo.”

Table 1. Comparison between fragments from the edict *vi bonorum raptorum* and *de naufragio*

Contrasting these three fragments will help us study some concrete issues such as the relation of the *edictum de naufragio* with the *vi bonorum raptorum*; the character and evolution of the *actio de naufragio*, and its relation to the *edictum de turba*. Finally, I will address the location of these provisions in the Digest regarding the *edictum de naufragio*. Apart from these dispositions, the edict of Lucullus is especially useful for dating and characterizing the *edictum de naufragio*¹³⁴.

At first glance, it can be observed that by mentioning *bona rapta*, the edict *vi bonorum raptorum* would also encompass *rapere* and *damnum dare*, conducts mentioned in the *edictum de naufragio*. As for *recipere*, that behaviour is included in *bona rapta* according to Balzarini, something evidenced by the use of *de cuius* in the edictal fragment¹³⁵. The relationship between the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* and the *actio de naufragio* lies essentially in the fact that both texts focus on the repression of *rapina*, using a similar treatment (*in quadruplum intra annum et post annum in simplum*). Otherwise, when reading the edict *de turba*, it is possible to appreciate that it aims to repress a specific conduct — perpetrating damage with *dolus malus* in the context of a crowd — something that allows me to think that this edict belongs to a chronological context similar to that of the *edictum de naufragio*. Besides, the criminalization of the *edictum de turba* is different from that of *de naufragio*. In fact, Cuiacius expressed very clearly that the *edictum de naufragio* was unnecessary because the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* covered the

134. Except for J.F. GERKENS, *o.c.* (n. 98). Besides, A. TARWACKA, *Romans and Pirates. Legal Perspective*, Warsaw, 2009, p. 106–109. Which mentions the *edictum de naufragio* but does not study it in detail.

135. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 415.

case included in this edict, and applied the same punishment¹³⁶. Both provisions dealt with the hypothesis of *rapina*, and both titles' 47.8 and 47.9 include when the subject removed, moved or received another person's property with *dolus malus*, or committed damage in cases of fire, shipwreck or assaulted ship. In relation to these statements, I am facing two other questions: why was the *edictum de naufragio* included in the Digest when this disposition was already covered by the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*? In addition, why would the *actio de naufragio* be placed after the *actio vi bonorum* if it was enacted later?

An article written by d'Ors and Santacruz in relation to the *actio iniuriarum*, explains the reason for maintaining the *actio de naufragio* in the Digest despite the fact that it was overtaken by the other *actio*¹³⁷. The authors affirmed, based on the texts of Ulpian and Labeo about the special edict of diffamation¹³⁸, that to preserve both edicts in the compilation was unnecessary because it could be included in the scope of the general *actio iniuriarum*¹³⁹. Both jurists justify that assertion mainly because the special edict was older, and later the praetor approved a general action to cover a bigger number of cases. Here, the special action would not have been abolished, because it would have seemed that they intended to eliminate such *actio*. They also indicated that the existence of a special edict was justified because the praetor wanted to preserve the action punishing that particular case, because if the event was not punished especially it could be forgotten and there was no other disposition dealing with these sort of events¹⁴⁰. In its case, the *actio de naufragio*

136. J. CUIACIUS, *Opera omnia in decem tomos distributa*, III, Paris, 1837, p. 293–294: “*Hoc edictum non est necessarium in raptorem, cum sufficiat superius, sed est etiam in quadruplum actio ex hoc edicto in eum, qui ex his causis abstulit, vel amovit, rem aliquam, vel qui recepit dolo malo, vel damnum dedit. Et de incendio, ruina ecc id est, de his, qui incendio, vel naufragio, aut rate expugnata, rapuisse vel per has causas damnum dedisse dicuntur, l. 1.3 de feriis, quod Labeo trahit etiam ad domum et villam expugnatam, l. in eum, C. de fur ex hoc additam poenae statutae olim recte; nam et Ulp. 1.1. de his facinoribus esse criminum executiones corporales poenas scilicet, et his novissime praetorem adidisse pecuniarios, quod etiam fecit titulo superiore*”; also talks about that J.F. GERKENS, *o.c.* (n. 98), p. 3–4.

137. A. D'ORS, J. SANTACRUZ, “A propósito de los edictos especiales *de iniuriis*”, *AHDE* 49 (1979), p. 655.

138. D. 47.10.15.26 (Ulp. 77 *ad ed.*).

139. A.D. MANFREDINI, *Contributi allo studio dell'iniuria in età repubblicana*, Milan, 1977, p. 115–116.

140. Another case illustrating my argument is the *edictum de fluminibus retardis* (establishing an *action in factum* for the *conductores* not fulfilling their duty of cleaning the river), not included in the perpetual edict of Hadrian but mentioned by Gell. 11.7.2. The lack of inclusion of this disposition in the edictal compilation could be because both Augustus and Tiberius established a *cura riparum* with its consequent liabilities and punishments, cf. A. LONARDI, *La cura riparum et alvei Tiberis. Storiografia, prosopografia e fonti epigrafiche*, Oxford, 2013, p. 9–14. About this edict, see R. VIGANO, “Sull'edictum de fluminibus retardis”, *Labeo* 15 (1969), p. 168–177; B. ALBANESE, “L'edictum vetus su qui flumina retanda publice redempta habent”, in *AUPA* 41 (1991), p. 19–29.

was still a useful norm, something that I can verify since the *naufragio* appears to be punished in later fragments, which are listed in table 4¹⁴¹.

As for the Digest's location of the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* in relation to the *actio de naufragio*, I believe that the fundamental criterion that could have moved the compilers to place both actions in such a way is a conception that goes from the general to the particular. It seems clear that the compilers followed a systematic classification from the general to the particular, since it can be evaluated in the following fragments (47.1 *iniuriis* of 47 and § 11), what included the extraordinary case of *iniuria* among other cases. In accordance with that, I consider that the compilers have proceeded to place the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* before the *actio de naufragio*.

Another problem is that in the title 47.8 I find collected both the *edictum de vi bonorum raptorum* and the *de turba*. While the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* covered the cases of damage and theft committed with the occasion of catastrophe, the edict *de turba* only dealt with the cases of damage committed during or because of *turba*. As I see it, the texts have been ordered from the general to the particular; a fact that is evident in the inclusion of fr. 4.9 (Ulp. 56 *ad ed.*) of title 47.8, which states:

loquitur autem hoc edictum de danno dato et de amisso, de rapto non: sed superiori edicto vi bonorum raptorum agi poterit.

This edict talks about the damage caused and of what was lost, not of the stolen goods: while in regard to theft, the superior edict can be used about goods stolen using violence.

The edict *de turba* belongs to a sort of provisions aiming to penalize specific situations like the *edictum de naufragio* or the edict of Lucullus. That would mean that this edict existed before the *edictum de vi bonorum raptorum*. However, if the comment belongs to Ulpian, who followed the order of the perpetual edict, it would indicate that this edict followed the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*. However, there is no other fragment of Ulpian collated in the Digest that reflect this sort of statements. Another possibility is that the compilers, who organized the edicts from those containing the most general to the most specific cases introduced it. This fragment has been conceived as interpolated by Balzarini, who indicates that what was mentioned in the fragment as if it were an explanatory comment was evidence that it can only be added by a compiler¹⁴². Vacca, on the other hand, argues that this fragment deals with the difference between both actions focusing on the *damnum*, so she does not believe that the fragment was alien to the classic content of the action¹⁴³.

141. N. TAMASSIA, *Stranieri ed Ebrei nell'Italia Meridionale dall'età Romana alla Sveva*, Venice, 1904, p. 793, indicating that this provision appears recurrently in the sources, which shows in the part of the riverside areas.

142. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 376–383.

143. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 3–4.

The *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, due to the general extent of the behaviors contained in it, seems to correspond to a different period from that of the *actio de naufragio* and *de turba*, which both include specific cases. The problem is that, as I know, Ulpian wrote his comments *ad edictum* following Hadrian's *edictum perpetuum*, which included the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* in the version which took a broader case than the one collected in the edict of Lucullus. This was also the version that appears compiled in the Digest and explains why I can think that Ulpian was referring to the edict of Lucullus and not to the *vi bonorum raptorum* edict. I will devote the following paragraphs to tracing the evolution of the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, with which I will understand better the reason for Ulpian's comment and its relation to the *de naufragio* and *de turba* edicts.

As can be seen in table 1, the text of D. 47.9.1*pr.* described the event pursued in the edict and its punishment, while in the case of the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, these elements must be reconstructed through two texts. This sort of punishment is not directly mentioned, which can be justified by the fact that this edict was preceded by Lucullus' edict (76 BC)¹⁴⁴, although Cicero already mentioned the *in quadruplum* penalty in his *Pro Tullio* speech¹⁴⁵. The text included in the note describes the historical needs that the edict had to satisfy, as was intended to stop the continuous looting that the families of slaves¹⁴⁶, assembled in armed bands, carried out in houses located in the countryside. These actions not only implied a risk for private subjects, but also a danger to public safety. In her study of Lucullus' edict

144. L. LABRUNA, o.c. (n. 38), p. 19–20: “colpiva in modo più rigoroso ipotesi forse già previste dalla lex Aquilia (seconda metà del s. III av. J-C.), e da esso mosse la giurisprudenza per la individuazione del delitto di rapina.”

145. The text appears in Cic. *Pro Tullio*, 8–12: *Cum omnes leges omniaque iudicia quae paulo graviora atque asperiora videntur esse ex improborum iniquitate et iniuria nata sunt, tum hoc iudicium paucis hisce annis propter hominum malam consuetudinem nimiamque licentiam constitutum est. nam cum multae familiae dicerentur in agris longinquis et pascuis armatae esse caedisque facere, cumque ea consuetudo non solum ad res privatorum sed 1 ad summam rem publicam pertinere videretur, M. Lucullus, qui summa aequitate et 2 sapientia ius dixit, primus hoc iudicium composuit et id spectavit ut omnes ita familias suas continerent ut non modo armati damnum nemini darent verum etiam lacessiti iure se potius quam armis defenderent; et cum sciret de damno legem esse Aquiliam, tamen hoc ita existimavit, apud maiores nostros cum et res et cupiditates minores essent et familiae non magnae magno metu continerentur ut perraro fieret ut homo occideretur, idque nefarium ac singulare facinus putaretur, nihil opus fuisse iudicio de vi coactis armatisque hominibus; quod enim usu non veniebat, de eo si quis legem aut iudicium constitueret, non tam prohibere videretur quam admonere. his temporibus cum ex bello diuturno atque domestico res in eam consuetudinem venisset ut homines minore religione armis uterentur, necesse putavit esse et in universam familiam iudicium dare, quod a familia factum diceretur, et recuperatores dare, ut quam primum res iudicaretur, et poenam graviolem constituere, ut metu comprimeretur audacia, et illam latebram tollere: “damnum iniuria” quod in aliis causis debet valere et valet lege Aquilia, id ex huius modi damno quod vi per servos armatos datum esset...* (lacking seven lines).

146. According to S. GALBOTTI, o.c. (n. 53), p. 17, the edict might have also included the *liberi* and not just the slaves.

and its origin¹⁴⁷, Vacca mentions the increase in slave labour as a result of the great conquests or the expansion of states as some key facts provoking the increase of violence perpetrated by bands of armed slaves¹⁴⁸.

The reconstructions of the edict in relation to the fragment contained in the Digest and the text of Cicero pointed out some decisive differences between the two texts. These fragments are gathered in table 2:

<p>Cic. <i>Pro Tullio</i>, 7–12: <i>Iudicium vestrum est, recuperatores quantae pecuniae paret dolo malo familiae P. Fabi vi hominibus armatis coactisve damnum datum esse m. Tullio. Eius rei taxationem nos fecimus; aestimatio vestra est; iudicium datum est in quadruplum.</i></p>	<p>47.8.2pr. (Ulp. libr 56 <i>ad ed.</i>) Praetor ait: “<i>Si cui dolo malo hominibus coactis damni quid factum esse dicetur sive cuius bona rapta esse dicentur, in eum, qui id fecisse dicetur, iudicium dabo. Item si servus fecisse dicetur, in dominum iudicium noxale dabo.</i>”</p>
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Table 2. Comparison of the fragment Cic. *Pro Tullio* mentioned in the *edictum de Lucullo* with a fragment of the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*

Comparing these fragments highlights their differences, which is useful to establish the relationship between the edict of Lucullus (76 BC), and the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*. One of the first recognizable differences is that, according to Lucullus’ edict, men who committed the damage had to be armed. Besides, it is evident that the case included in the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* was broader, including not only the supposed damage done by gangs but also the cases of goods stolen employing violence. The differences between texts have led the authors to propose very different theories.

Some have argued that the Digest’ fragment is the combination of two edicts (*dolo malo hominibus armatis coactisve damnum datum* and *bona vi rapta*)¹⁴⁹.

147. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 521–524, the solution to the fact that the conquered lands were usually found in isolated places was the acquisition of slaves that was easy to do, because of the massive provision resulting from the conquests. The inhuman conditions in which these slaves live led to frequent riots, looting or acts of rapine. Cato. *Agr.*, I. 7 talks about the importance of the farmer treating his slaves well so that crops can be tended properly (*familiae male en sit, en algeat, en esuriat, opere bene exerceat uilicus si nolet male facere, non faciet*).

148. K. HOPKINS, *Conquerors and Slaves*, Cambridge, 1978, p. 7–10. He isolates seven processes for which he considers the growth of slavery in the Republic took place, of which some have been mentioned previously: continuous war, spoils, investments in land, expansion of territories, impoverishment of the peasants, their emigration and the growth of urban markets, and similarly, E.M. STAERMAN, “Storia della schiavitù della tarda Repubblica Romana”, in *Schiavitù e produzione nella Roma Repubblicana*, Roma, 1986, p. 165–189. And concerning the public land, see S. ROSELAAR, *Public Land in the Roman Republic: A Social and Economic History of Ager Publicus in Italy*, 396–89 BC, Oxford, 2010, p. 155–166.

149. Authors such as M. CRAMER, “M. Tulli Ciceronis orationis pro Tullio fragmentum ineditum”, in *M. Tulli Ciceronis orationum pro Scauro, pro Tulio, pro Flacco partes ineditae cum scholiis ad orationem pro Scauro item ineditis, cum emendationibus et comentariis*, Leipzig, 1816,

Among these authors, there are divergent opinions about whether the modification of both provisions in order to create the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, occurred on a date between 71 BC (Cic. *Pro Tullio*) and 131 AD (codification of the perpetual edict by Julian)¹⁵⁰; or the reconstruction was the work of a post-classical jurist or a Justinian compiler¹⁵¹. On the other hand, Serrao indicates that possibly a first edict was approved in 76 BC, which was specified and better bound by a later praetor, and that it was this edict that was included in the perpetual edict of Julian¹⁵². On the other hand, other studies indicate that the edict was provided for the cases of damage and robbery, and that these behaviours could be punished by a single action, so that rapine would fall within the assumption of Lucullus' edict, in which only *damnum* was mentioned¹⁵³. According to Rouvier¹⁵⁴, the edict underwent a first evolution that combined the *actio furti* and the *actio ex lege Aquilia*, so the original *actio* was expanding in a way that covered the rapine committed either by one or several subjects. In a second evolution, the repression that was reflected in the edict could have been extended by *reipersecutoriae* actions, so according to Rouvier, it could be described as a mixed action, a concept that was labelled in the Justinianic era¹⁵⁵.

p. 67; hypothesis sustained by M. COHN, *Zum Römischen Vereinsrecht. Abhandlungen aus der Rechtsgeschichte*, Berlin, 1873, p. 187ss., who thinks that these edicts were merged by the Justinian compilers; F.C. VON SAVIGNY, "Über Cicero *Pro Tullio* und die *actio vi bonorum raptorum*", *ZSS* 5 (1825), p. 123–130. Th. MOMMSEN, *Römisches Strafrecht*, Leipzig, 1899, p. 660–671; O. Lenel, *EP*³, p. 391–393. U. EBERT *Die Geschichte des Edikts de hominibus armatis coactisve*, Heidelberg, 1968, p. 127–132. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 58–65, bases his opinion on the consideration that in no way could the notion of edictal law, being in close relationship with the *lex Aquilia*, have included in its origin the species of the subtraction, therefore the union of two edicts became necessary; and he adds in his study "Cic. *Pro Tullio* e l'editto di Lucullo", in *Studi Grosso* I, Turin, 1968, p. 378–379, that in his opinion, the assumption approved by the praetor Lucullus only included the damage caused by armed bands. The fact that Cicero mentions rapine in the *Pro Tullio* would be a resource used by the speaker, appreciable in various works of his, with the intention of expressing fear, desolation or devastation.

150. In that case, changing the name of the provision by including it in the perpetual edict, A. WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 43), p. 106.
151. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 46–47.
152. F. SERRAO, *La iurisdictio del pretore peregrino*, Milan, 1954, p. 77.
153. F. KELLER, *Semestrium ad M. Tullium Ciceronem libri sex*, I, 3, Turin, 1851, p. 541–543; Ph.M. HUSCHKE, *M. Tullii Ciceronis orationis pro M. Tulio quae extant, cum comentariis et excursibus*, Leipzig, 1826, p. 195–197; P. HUVELIN, *Cours élémentaire de droit romain*, II, Paris, 1929, p. 37, and in a similar way, *Études sur le furtum dans le très ancien droit romain*, Lyon/Paris, 1915, p. 804, n. 4; F. SERRAO, *o.c.* (n. 152), p. 77–80.
154. J. ROUVIER, "Remarques sur l'*actio vi bonorum raptorum*", *RHD* 41 (1963), p. 448–452: "le mot rapina constituée donc à nos yeux une manière de pont jeté par Cicéron entre l'*actio* nouvelle, telle que l'a créée Terentius, et telle qu'elle nous apparaîtra au cours de la première de ses deux évolutions."
155. I. 4.6.16. *Sequens illa divisio est, quod quaedam actiones rei persequendae gratia comparatae sunt, quaedam poenae persequendae, quaedam mixtae sunt*, also § 20 indicates *Quaedam actiones*

What has been explained in the previous paragraph can be explained through the historical evolution of the edict, which would go from only punishing the illicit damage committed by gangs of armed slaves, to also include violent robbery¹⁵⁶. Vacca also denies that this action was the result of the evolution of two successive edicts, but that it was just one edict with a scope that covered a wider number of actions¹⁵⁷. In fact, I think that violent robbery is included in *damnum*, since it is more logical that the praetor would not have taken care to provide for an aggravated penalty for the *damnum* committed in the circumstances of the edict without taking into account robbery, which was a common behaviour¹⁵⁸. In Vacca's opinion, Cicero indicated that in his speech as *iudicium de vi coactis armatisque hominibus*, which was equivalent to “editto diretto cioè a reprimere la violenza posta in essere da uomini armati riuniti in bande, violenza che poteva concretarsi sia in danneggiamenti, sia in rapine, sia in spossessamenti e distruzioni¹⁵⁹.” Vacca thought that the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* was an edict created *ex novo*, although she understood that the edict presented substantial differences from Lucullus' edict in its later development, so this evolution would have been motivated by different social needs¹⁶⁰. According to her, while the Republic sought to tackle situations through the repression of a specific situation (e.g. damage committed by an armed gang), with the arrival of the principate there was an increase in the power of criminal repression in situations that endangered individual security and social peace¹⁶¹.

mixtam causam optinere videntur tam in rem quam in personam. Qualis est familiae erciscundae actio, quae competit coheredibus de dividenda hereditate: item communi dividundo, quae inter eos redditur, inter quos aliquid commune est, ut id dividatur: item finium regundorum, quae inter eos agitur, qui confines agros habent. In quibus tribus iudiciis permittitur iudici rem alicui ex litigatoribus ex bono et aequo adiudicare et, si unius pars praegravari videbitur, eum invicem certa pecunia alteri condemnare; P. DE FRANCISCI, *Studi sulle azioni penali e la loro intramissibilità passiva*, Milan, 1912, a criminal action is one that comes from crime, and seeks the restitution of the thing, or compensation for damage. Justinian altered this concept, distinguishing between criminal action, *reipersecutoria* or mixed action; A. AUDIBERT, “Nouvelle étude sur la formule des actions *familiae erciscundae* et *communi dividundo*”, *NRH* 28 (1904), p. 407–411. U. VON LÜTBOW, *Edikstittel quod metus causa*, Greifswald, 1932, p. 292; P. VOCI, *Risarcimento e pena privata nel diritto romano classico*, Milan, 1939, p. 91; H. ANKUM, “Gaius, Theophilus and Tribonian and the *actiones mixtae*”, in P. STEIN (ed.), *Studies in Justinian's Institutes in Memory of J.A.C. Thomas*, London, 1983, p. 4–18.

156. G. BROGGINI, *L'orazione per Marco Tullio*, Rome, 1964, p. 379–81.

157. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 2–12.

158. Following this approach, L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 6–10; M. MARRONE, *Istituzioni di diritto romano*³, Palermo, 2006, p. 504–506; S. GALEOTTI, *o.c.* (n. 52), p. 19; *contra*: M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 56–57.

159. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 532–533.

160. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 97–101.

161. P. HUVELIN, *Études d'histoire du droit commercial romain : histoire externe-droit maritime*, Paris, 1929, p. 85–89, gives a number of actions in the edict that cover the assumptions of *furtum* and *damnum*. The consistent process by the praetor to join the *furtum* and *damnum* in the edict and in the formula constitutes a work of simplification and unification.

In this way, the initial demand for actions punishing concrete events (such as the *edictum de naufragio*) was gradually lost. During the Principate, the praetor tried to protect individual security, giving relevance to the diverse fields connected with *vis*, extending the application of this concept into more general fields. The jurists made special efforts to cover violent theft, which was also comparable to robbery committed in the occasion of a catastrophe¹⁶². The maintenance of the expression *dolo malo hominibus (armatis) coactis (ve) in actio vi bonorum raptorum* would be a remainder of the original Lucullus edict, but the presence of armed gangs would not be an essential requirement in the new provision.

In short, once the original *ratio* that justified the existence of that edict was superseded, the disposition had a broader repressive focus in the subsequent evolution¹⁶³. These differences could be attributed to a jurisprudential elaboration affected by a diverse social and political reality that influenced the approval of Lucullus' edict. Having dispensed with the need for a private criminal action against violence, and qualified by the use of weapons or its performance by violent groups, the jurists proceeded to extend the conducts addressed in an edict so that it could cover a greater number of cases of violent theft. Therefore, the use of violence remained the element that qualified the assumptions that fell within the scope of the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*.

Once these different theories about the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* are explained, it can be understood why the behaviour addressed in the *edictum de naufragio* could be covered by the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*. This conception can be seen in later texts that mention violent robbery, as is the case with Gaius¹⁶⁴ and Papinian¹⁶⁵. The edict was approved in the context of crisis, and so the assumptions reflected in it were common at the time. In the end, this edict was clearly connected to the late Republican period in the history of Rome, and it is revealed to be insufficient to cover the various assumptions involving violent theft. In the title 47.9, the violence of the offender's acts was based on the fact that they took advantage of a catastrophic situation. In the edict, *vis* was understood as an event that paralyzed the resistance of the subject to seize back his property. Thus, *vis* entailed the violation of property rights on assets that still belonged to the original owner and were affected by the catastrophic situation¹⁶⁶.

162. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 52–60; 105.

163. The reconstruction of the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* from M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 345, is very similar to the one reconstructed by Lenel for the *actio de naufragio*.

164. Gai. 3.109: *cuius dolo fuerit raptum, furti quidem non tenebitur, sed vi bonorum raptorum*.

165. D.47.2.81.4 (Papin. lib. 12 *quaest*): *Is autem, cuius dolo fuerit raptum, furti quidem non tenebitur, sed vi bonorum raptorum*. We do not rule out that in his turn Papinian, jurist of the 3rd cent. AD considered the assumption of an *actio* in the other.

166. L. VACCA, *Derelictio e acquisto delle res pro derelicto habitae: lettura delle fonti e tradizione sistematica*, Milan, 1984, p. 90–97, this is due to the erroneous consideration of the abandonment or dereliction of the things.

Rapina constituted a *delictum* also prosecuted by the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*. According to the *edictum de naufragio*, this behaviour seemed to have the *dolus malus* as its only essential feature, if I consider that the praetor himself added this requirement to *recipere* to make a comparison with the other two typical behaviours included in the edict of § 1*pr.* (*quid rapuisse recepisse dolo malo*). It will be Ulpian who will point out the link between the assumption established in Lucullus' edict, the *actio vi bonorum raptorum* and the *edictum de naufragio*. In § 3.5 the jurist said "*rapi autem sine vi no potest*", which would be a characteristic of the conduct *per se*, which qualified the *furtum*, so that the offender would be considered *fur improbior*¹⁶⁷, and their conduct as an arbitrary exercise of one's will consisting in the seizure of the property of others¹⁶⁸.

In this edict, both *vis* and *dolus malus* were elements that defined the unlawfulness of the conducts included in the provision¹⁶⁹. The praetor, intending to protect the subjects from suffering these situations, approved these edicts seeking the general elements that qualified the case, since the edict would easily be adapted to new cases¹⁷⁰. To understand why it could be necessary to have two edicts, I need to leave behind the conception that only considers the evolution of the edict of Lucullus to the *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, not conceiving the praetorian actions that had arisen during the course of the evolution from one edict to another. The key to the two edicts was because the *de naufragio* edict was enacted probably prior to the *vi bonorum raptorum* edict, and therefore covered a specific typical case similar to Lucullus' edict, which was also intended to protect a violent situation occurring in a specific historical context. In sum, from both edicts and their development I see the evolution of a first trend of the Republican jurisdiction towards the repression of concrete cases through private actions, to an interest in tutelage of more general situations connected with the concept of *vis*. The jurists made special efforts to cover violent theft, which was also comparable to other events associated with catastrophic situations¹⁷¹.

Another issue is to provide an exact dating for the *edictum de naufragio*, which I do not know with certainty whether it would have been approved before or after Lucullus' edict. As can be seen in table 4, I have located the edict *de turba* as coming before Lucullus' edict, because although it penalizes the behaviour carried out during situations of confusion, the penalty here is lesser than in Lucullus' edict. Follow-

167. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 281, 102; G. LONGO, *o.c.* (n. 97), p. 463.

168. M. BALZARINI, *o.c.* (n. 55), p. 90–91.

169. J. ROUVIER, *o.c.* (n. 154), p. 450, which also occurred in the edict of Lucullus, F. CANCELLI, *Il dolo nel diritto penale romano*, Milan, 1965, p. 43: "*L'editto luculliano aveva concentrato la qualifica della condotta, oltre che sulla vis e sugli hominibus armatis coactisve, soltanto nel dolo malo e non anche nell'iniuria.*"

170. L. VACCA, *Contributo allo studio del metodo casistico in diritto romano*, Naples, 1976, p. 133–139.

171. L. VACCA, *o.c.* (n. 72), p. 52–58; 105.

ing from this, it was possible that in the same repressive *spectrum*, Lucullus' edict — which maintained the penalty *in quadruplum* — was approved shortly afterwards. Also, I estimate that the *edictum de naufragio* could have been approved *a posteriori*, collecting a penalty equal to that of Lucullus' edict, and picking up a factual assumption in which not only the theft on the occasion of a catastrophe was collected, but, as said previously, the provocation of such a catastrophe. As has already been mentioned, this chronological order is hypothetical, although what seems to be a clear fact is the relationship between these three edicts and their chronological closeness.

5. Conclusion

The repressive aim pursued with the *edictum de naufragio* reflected how the historical context of the last century of the Republic supposed a perfect environment for the qualification and repression of violence (*vis*). In addition, *vis* was the unifying link of the *edictum de naufragio* with most of the legal sources approved in the last century of the Republic, which in fact helps me characterizing this concrete period of Roman history. As has been argued throughout this article, it is almost impossible to offer a completely certain dating for this edict (as with most sources from the Republic), but the evidence coming from other legal dispositions or historical events has made it possible to, at least, provide an accurate date range. The comparison of the *edictum de naufragio* with other dispositions highlighted several aspects of lawmaking in the late Republic.

One of the key points of this paper is to discuss how shipwrecks and associated criminal actions were addressed and punished by the Roman authorities. Here the *ius naufragii* aimed to protect shippers and consequently changed earlier maritime customs. The fragments contained in the title D. 47.9 (as well as other sources included in table 4) belong to different periods of Roman history, which indicates that once the Romans started punishing the previous practice of *ius naufragii*, this conception was maintained in later Roman sources. Then, after the fall of the Roman Empire, the *ius naufragii* reappears again as a common practice in different Mediterranean areas. As happened previous to the Roman conquest of the Mediterranean, the recovery of this practice indicates the existence of a fragmented Mediterranean composed of several areas holding different identities. Thus, the change in the conception of shipwrecking implied protection for the different subjects who were threatened by these sorts of practices. However, looking from a bird eye's view, it should also be seen as a sample of the Roman aim of constructing an empire which constituted a system, formed by diverse parts composing an integrated whole. These aims had long-term consequences for trade and transport that flourished during the Empire and helped to build navigational patterns and routes that lasted for more than three centuries.

Table 3. Key events in the evolution of the creation of the edict (following A. Watson. *o.c.* [n. 44])

Date	Event	Source(s)
367 BC	Approval of the <i>leges Licinia Sextiae</i> . Creation of the urban <i>praetura</i> , the praetor could approve edicts ¹ , but the development of this source of creation of law as such was not yet fully developed.	Livy 6. 30–42; D. 1.2.2.27 (Pomp. Lib. 1 <i>ench.</i>)
242 BC ²	Creation of the magistracy of the <i>praetor peregrinus</i>	D. 1.2.2.28 (Pomp. Lib. 1 <i>ench.</i>)
199–126 BC	<i>Lex Aebutia de formulis</i> . Abolition of the <i>legis actiones</i> — except those concerning the <i>centumviri</i> and in the case of <i>damnum infectum</i> — and the introduction of the formulary procedure. The reform was completed with the <i>leges Iuliae iudicariae</i> (17 BC). The reform served to generalize the formulary procedure, which was undoubtedly known before and practised in trials between foreigners.	Gai.4.30; Gell. 16.10
Circa 140 BC	Changes in the substantive law are not made through edicts, but through particular actions	Lenel, <i>EP</i> ³ , 115 (<i>actio de mandati</i>); Lenel, <i>EP</i> ³ , 205 (<i>actio in factum adversus nautas, caupones, stibularios</i>); Lenel. <i>EP</i> ³ .219 (<i>actio si mentor falsum modum dixerit</i>); Lenel. <i>EP</i> ³ .117 (<i>actio Serviana</i>)
140–100 BC	They started to approve edicts which modify the <i>ius civile</i> , although it is likely that these will be limited to restricting the rights of a plaintiff in a civil action	D. 13.6.5.3 (Ulp. 28 <i>ad ed.</i>) edict de <i>commodatum</i> ; D. 46.3.81.1 (Pomp. Lib. 1 <i>ench.</i>) edictum de <i>depositum</i>

1. A. WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 44), p. 111, indicates that both the urban and the peregrine praetors probably had *ius edicendi* from the moment of creation of their magistracies. He gives the *SC de Bacchanalibus* (186 BC.) as an example of the consolidation of this right.
2. According to T. C. BRENNAN, *o.c.* (n. 50), p. 86–87, the sources and the events of the time indicate that probably this magistrature was approved before the year 242 BC.

100 BC–27 BC	The years of highest edictal production ³ , although the highest peak of development had not reached its greatest development.	<i>Edictum de convicio</i> (<i>Ret ad her.</i> 4.25.35); edictal clauses providing <i>bonorum possessio</i> for several aims ⁴ (<i>Cic. Quint.</i> , 19.60); <i>edictum de hominibus armatis coactisve et vi bonorum raptorum</i> (<i>Cic. Pro Tullio</i> , 4.8) ⁵ ; <i>edictum de dolo</i> (<i>Cic. De nat. deor.</i> , 3.30.74); <i>edictum de pactis</i> (<i>Cic. Att.</i> , 2.9.1)
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Table 4. Texts that relate the words *incendio ruina naufragio*

Author, work, and fragment	Date	Text
<i>Cicero, Paradoxa Stoicorum</i> , 6.51.8	46 BC ⁶	<i>aestimanda virtus, quae nec eripi nec subripi potest neque naufragio neque incendio amittitur nec tempestatum nec temporum perturbatione mutatur! qua</i>
<i>Quint. Inst.</i> , 8.6.50.3	1 st cent. AD	<i>genere coeperis tralationis, hoc desinas. Multi autem, cum initium tempestatem sumpserunt, incendio aut ruina finiunt, quae est inconsequencia rerum foedissima.</i>
<i>Quint. Declam. Maior. [sp.]</i> , 9.16.23	1 st cent. AD	<i>quandam humanitatis civicam gloriam: periturum hominem, sive ille naufragio eiectus, seu spoliatus incendio sive exutus latrocinio erat, naturae patriaeque restitui.</i>
<i>Sen. Controv., excerpta</i> 5.1.pr.–2, 5.1.pr.–3	1 st cent. AD	<i>Inscripti maleficii sit actio. Quidam naufragio facto, amissis tribus liberis et uxore incendio domus, suspendit se. praecidit illi quidam ex praetereunitibus laqueum. a liberato reus fit maleficii.</i>
<i>Sen. Ben.</i> , 1.5.4.3, 1.5.4.4	1 st cent. AD	<i>hostis exceptit et in carcerem condidit: non beneficium, sed usum beneficium mei sustulit. Ex naufragio alicui raptos vel ex incendio liberos reddidi, hos vel morbus vel aliqua fortuita iniuria eripuit: manet etiam sine</i>

3. To the sources included in the table, I must add the mentions to other edicts made by jurists of the Republican era, such as Servius Sulpicius Rufus, who died in 43 BC (W. KUNKEL, *Herkunft und soziale Stellung der römischen Juristen*, Colonia, 2001, p. 25); Trebatius Testa and Ofilius (both from the 1st cent BC.). See A. WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 44), p. 109.
4. Like *qui fraudationis causa latitarit; cui heres non existabit; qui exilii causa solum verterit*, all of them created around 81 BC.
5. 76 BC (see Tables 5 and 6 and section 4.1).
6. D. MEHL, “The Stoic paradoxes according to Cicero”, in J.F. MILLER, C. DAMON, S.K. MYERS (eds.), *Vertis in usum*, Munich, 2002, p. 39.

D. 44.7.1.4.4 (Gaius lib. 2 aur.)	2 nd cent. AD	<i>minus obligatus permanet: is uero qui utendum accepit, si maiore casu, cui humana infirmitas resistere non potest, ueluti incendio ruina naufragio, rem quam accepit amisit, securus est. alias tamen exactissiman diligentiam custodiendae rei praestare compellitur</i>
D. 2.12.3pr. (Ulp. 2 ad ed.)	3 rd cent. AD	<i>Solet etiam messis vindemiarumque tempore ius dici de rebus quae tempore vel morte periturae sunt. Morte: ueluti furti: damni iniuriae: iniuriarum atrocium: qui de incendio ruina naufragio rate nave expugnata rapuisse dicuntur: et si quae similes sunt. Item si res tempore periturae sunt aut actionis dies exiurus est.</i>
D. 2.13.6.9 (Ulp. 4 ad ed.)	3 rd cent. AD	<i>Prohibet argentario edi illa ratione, quod etiam ipse instructus esse potest instrumento suae professionis: et absurdum est, cum ipse in ea sit causa, ut edere debeat, ipsum petere ut edatur ei. An nec heredi argentarii edi ratio debeat, videndum: et si quidem instrumentum argentariae ad eum peruenit, non debet ei edi, si minus, edenda est ex causa. Nam et ipsi argentario ex causa ratio edenda est: si naufragio vel ruina vel incendio vel alio simili casu rationes perdidisse probet aut in longinquo habere, ueluti trans mare.</i>
D. 2.15.8.25 (Ulp. 5 de omn. Trib.)	3 rd cent. AD	<i>Si ad habitationem certa quantitas sit annua relicta et ita sit transactum sine praetore, ut habitatio praestetur, ualet transactio, quia fructus habitationis praestatur, licet ruinae vel incendio subiecta transactio est. Per contrarium quoque si pro habitatione, quae erat relicta, placuerit certam quantitatem praestari, transactio rata est et citra praetorem.</i>
D. 16.3.1.1 (Ulp. 30 ad ed.)	3 rd cent. AD	<i>Praetor ait: "Quod neque tumultus neque incendii neque ruinae neque naufragii causa depositum sit, in simplum, earum autem rerum, quae supra comprehensae sunt, in ipsum in duplum, in heredem eius, quod dolo malo eius factum esse dicitur qui mortuus sit, in simplum, quod ipsius, in duplum iudicium dabo."</i>
D. 24.1.32.14 (Ulp. 33 ad Sab.)	3 rd cent. AD	<i>si ante mors contigerit ei cui donatum est, nullius momenti donationem esse uoluit: ergo si ambo decesserint, quid dicemus, naufragio forte uel ruina uel incendio? et si quidem possit apparere, quis ante spiritum posuit, expedita est quaestio: sin uero non appareat,</i>
Paul. Sent., 2.4.2	4 th cent. AD	<i>Si factio incendio ruina naufragio aut quo alio simili casu res commodata amissa sit, non tenebitur eo nomine is cui commodata est, nisi forte, cum posset rem commodatam saluam facere, suam praetulit</i>

Paul. Sent., 5.3.2	4 th cent. AD	Quidquid ex incendio ruina naufragio navique expugnata raptum susceptum suppressumve erit, eo anno in quadruplum eius rei, quam quis suppresserit celaverit rapuerit, convenitur, postea in simplum.
I. 3.14.2	6 th cent. AD	Item is cui res aliqua utenda datur, id est commodatur, re obligatur et tenetur commodati actione. sed is ab eo qui mutuum accepit longe distat: namque non ita res datur, ut eius fiat, et ob id de ea re ipsa restituenda tenetur. et is quidem qui mutuum accepit, si quolibet fortuito casu quod accepit amiserit, veluti incendio ruina naufragio aut latronum hostiumve incursu, nihilo minus obligatus permanet. at is qui utendum accepit sane quidem exactam diligentiam custodiendae rei praestare iubetur nec sufficit ei tantam diligentiam adhibuisse, quantum suis rebus adhibere solitus est, si modo alius diligentior poterit eam rem custodire: sed propter maiorem vim maioresve casus non tenetur, si modo non huius culpa is casus intervenerit: alioquin si id quod tibi commodatum est peregre ferre tecum malueris et vel incursu praedonumve vel naufragio amiseris, dubium non est, quin de restituenda ea re tenearis. commodata autem res tunc proprie intellegitur, si nulla mercede accepta vel constituta res tibi utenda data est. alioquin mercede interveniente locatus tibi usus rei videtur: gratuitum enim debet esse commodatum.
C. 6.2.18	6 th cent. AD	Imperatores Diocletianus, Maximianus. In eum, qui ex naufragio vel incendio cepisse vel in his rebus damni quid dedisse dicitur, infra annum utilem ei cui res abest quadrupli, post in simplum actionem proditam praeter poenam olim statutam edicti forma perpetui declarat. * DIOCL. ET MAXIM. AA. ET CC. DIONYSODORO. * <A 294 S. III K. IAN. NICOMEDIAE CC. CONSS. >

Table 5. Legal dispositions approved in the Republic that helped to establish the features of the development praetorian edict

Legal disposition	Dating	Comments	Sources
Edictum <i>Nautae caupones et stabularius</i>	2 nd cent. BC.	It is not possible to date the edict with greater precision. By studying external factors, determining the development of the Roman maritime traffic, I can hypothesize that the disposition belongs to the 2 nd cent. BC. At this moment, it was necessary to develop the appropriate legal dispositions to address navigation, bearing in mind that these dispositions were not yet using the <i>locatio operis</i> . Servius Sulpicius Rufus died in 43 BC, and knew of the <i>edictum ne quid infamandi causa</i> , and of the edict introduced by the <i>actio institoria</i> . If I understand that this <i>actio</i> was older than the <i>actio exercitoria</i> , which in turn is less ancient than the <i>receptum nautarum cauponum stabulariorum</i> ⁷ , I understand that the two edicts relating to these actions should also have existed.	[D. 4, 9] Gaius 5 <i>ad ed. provinc.</i> Paul 13 <i>ad ed.</i> ; Paul 22 <i>ad ed.</i> ; Ulp. 14 <i>ad ed.</i> ; Ulp. 18 <i>ad ed.</i> ;
<i>Bonae fidei actiones de tutelae, empti, venditi, Locati, conducti, pro socio y mandati</i>	2 nd cent. BC?	The order of development of actions of good faith is still a controversial issue. However, it is admitted by most of the doctrine that the <i>Bonae fidei actiones de tutelae, empti, venditi, Locati, conducti, pro socio and mandati</i> for which there were no preserved edictal institutions by which I can indicate with total certainty that these shares belonged to the 2 nd cent. BC. The commercial development that Rome experienced during this period serves as an indicator of the development of these provisions.	[D. 19,2] Paul. 34 <i>ad ed.</i> ; Gaius lib. 2 <i>rerum cottidianarum sive aureorum; libro 10 ad ed. prov.</i> ; Pomp. lib. 9 et 6 <i>ad Sabinum; Ulp. 28 ad ed.; Paul 32 ad ed.</i> ; Tryph. Lib.9 <i>disputationem</i> .
<i>Formula Octaviana</i>	79–76 BC ⁸	Remedy had sought to protect citizens with force or fear. It was a precedent for the <i>actio quod metus causa</i> (D. 4, 2, 14, 3).	Cic. 2 <i>Ver.</i> 2,3; 65; 152; Cic. <i>Q. fr.</i> , 1.1.21

7. Cf. J. J. AUBERT, *Business Managers in Ancient Rome*, Leiden/New York/Köln, 1994, p. 72–73.8. S. GALEOTTI, *o.c.* (n. 53), p. 18 provides the same date of enactment as us.

<i>Edictum de metus</i>	78 BC	Introduced by the praetor Octavius, consul in the year 75 BC. This <i>actio</i> was focused on the restitution of property taken, with a penalty of four times its value (as it was <i>formula octaviana</i>). It was only approved in cases of real extortion, and at a later stage the <i>actio quod metus causa</i> covered the cases of third parties.	Cic. <i>Off.</i> , 3.29.103; 3.30.110; Q. <i>fr.</i> , 1.1.21; <i>Ver.</i> 3.65.152; D. 4.2.1; D. 4.2.5 (Ulp. 11 <i>ad ed.</i>)
<i>Edictum de turba</i>	?	Its approach is inherited from the <i>lex Aquilia</i> , but focuses on a specific case of damage caused to the property of another in cases of turmoil.	D. 47.8.4 <i>pr.</i> ; D. 47.8.4.9; <i>EP</i> ³ § 188
<i>Edictum de Luculo</i>	76 BC	Introduced as the <i>iudicium de vi coactis armatisque hominibus</i> , it is probably the origin of the <i>actio vi bonorum raptorum</i> (<i>EP</i> ³ § 187).	Asc. 75; Cic. <i>Pro Tull.</i> , 3–12
<i>Edictum de incendio, ruina naufragio rae nave expugnata</i>	?	This criminal action addresses the risk by attempting to criminalize the theft using violence (<i>rapina</i>) committed during a catastrophe.	<i>EP</i> ³ § 189; [D. 47.9] Ulp. 56 <i>ad ed.</i> Paul 54 <i>ad ed.</i> ; Gai 21 <i>ad ed. prov.</i> Call. 1 <i>ad ed mon.</i> Call. 2 <i>quaest.</i> ; Nerat. Lib 2 <i>resp.</i> Marc. 14 <i>inst.</i> ; PS V, 3, 2; Cic. <i>Paradoxa stoicorum</i> 51
<i>Interdictio de vi armata</i>	73–72 BC	It was a provision that sought to regain possession in favour of those who had been violently dispossessed of their property by a group of armed men.	Cic. <i>Fam.</i> , 7.13.2; Cic. <i>Caec.</i> , 69 a.C.; Cic. <i>Pro Tull.</i> (71 a.C.), 46 ^o
<i>Edictum de dolo malo</i>	66 BC ¹⁰	Penalized behaviours committed with bad intent (<i>dolo malo</i>), and introduced an <i>actio in factum</i> for the punishment of these facts.	D. 4.3.1.1 (Ulp. 11 <i>ad ed.</i>); D. 43.4.1 (Ulp. 72 <i>ad ed.</i>); Cic. <i>Off.</i> , 3.60; <i>Nat.</i> D. 3.30.74.

9. If Cicero mentions it in his speech as *actio vi bonorum raptorum*, this reveals that the interdict must be a little earlier.

10. Cicero indicates that Aquilius Gallus (*praetor* in 66 BC) approved this edict, but I know that it dealt with the *quaestio de ambitu*, reason why the edict should have been approved more or less around that date. A. WATSON, *o.c.* (n. 39), p. 32, n. 2, who says that Gallus had created this edict when he was in charge of a *quaestio de ambitu*. However, C. BRENNAN, *o.c.* (n. 50), p. 463, argues that he had prepared the formula during its charge, but that this edict should have been approved later.

<i>Edictum de vi bonorum raptorum et armatis coactisve</i>	131 AD?	In my opinion, this extension of Lucullus' edict corresponds to the legislative tendency that is also noticeable in the edict concerning bad intent. It introduced penalties for criminal actions in situations that covered a broad perspective, including many situations that covered cases of robbery with violence.	<i>EP</i> ³ § 188; D. 47.8.2pr.; Ulp. 56 ad ed. Paul 54 ad ed.
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Table 6. Some of the most important provisions of 1st cent. BC in relation to violence and that help to date the edict *de naufragio*

Legal disposition	Dating	Comments	Sources
<i>Lex Cornelia de sicariis et veneficiis</i>	81 BC	It provided sanctions for those individuals who caused the death of others through certain means such as the use of fire. It extended the typical case to other situations such as shipwreck, as can be seen in D.47.9.3.8	D.48.8; I.4.18; PS. V. 23.1; Cic. <i>Cluent.</i> , 54; CTh. 9.14; C. 9.16.5; Coll. 1.3.1-2
<i>Lex Cornelia de iniuriis</i>	81 BC	Penalized three types of wounds caused by violence: <i>pulsare</i> (hit), <i>verberare</i> (whip) and <i>domum introire</i> (forced entry into another person's house).	D.47.10.5pr.; D.48.2.23; D.48.5.8; PS, V, 4;
<i>Lex Plautia de vi</i>	78-63 BC	First law established against the crime <i>vis</i> committed against the state or an individual subject. Penalized for example armed men who entered the Senate or violence committed against magistrates.	Sall. <i>Cat.</i> 31.4; Cic. <i>Cael.</i> , 29.70; 70.1; <i>Mil.</i> 13.35; <i>Har. Resp.</i> , 8.15; <i>Fam.</i> , 8.8; <i>Q. fr.</i> , 2.3; <i>Att.</i> , 2.24; <i>Ascon.</i> 55; <i>Gai.</i> 2.45; <i>Quint. Inst. Or.</i> 9.3.56; D.41.3.33.2 (<i>Iul. 33 digest.</i>)
<i>Lex Gabinia de bello pinatico</i>	67 BC	Law approved in favour of Pompeyo Magno by which an <i>imperium infinitum</i> was conferred on him to initiate his fight against piracy.	Cic. <i>Leg. Man.</i> 15-23; <i>Ascon.</i> 72a-c; <i>Livius, Per. XCIX</i> ; <i>Dio</i> ; <i>Cass. XXXVI</i> ; <i>Eutr.</i> VI.13; <i>Val. Max.</i> VIII. 15; <i>D.</i> 36.23; <i>App. Mith.</i> 94
<i>Lex Cornelia de Iurisdictione</i>	67 BC	It forbade the praetors from modifying their edict by means of <i>edicta repentina</i> approved during their year of office or acting against the principles established by their edict.	<i>FIRA.</i> II. 1909. 69; <i>Dio.</i> <i>Cass.</i> 36.40.1-2; <i>Ascon.</i> 58